

```

# Greenspace mitigates the global disease and economic burdens of non-communicable diseases
# R code
# R version 4.3.1
# 2025.05.30

loc_file <- "E:/Greenspace_NCDs/data"
loc_save <- "E:/Greenspace_NCDs/result"

#####
## Data preprocessing
#####

# 1. Outcome: disease burden of non-communicable diseases (NCDs)
# indices: age-standardized rates of deaths, DALYs (Disability-Adjusted Life Years), YLLs (Years
Lived with Disability), and YLDs (Years of Life Lost)
# source: GBD 2021
setwd(loc_file)
Outcome_1 <- read.csv("IHME-GBD_2021_DATA-f15f9fa8-1.csv")
Outcome_1$measure_name[Outcome_1$measure_name=="DALYs (Disability-Adjusted Life Years)"]
<- "DALYs"
Outcome_1$measure_name[Outcome_1$measure_name=="YLDs (Years Lived with Disability)"] <-
"YLDs"
Outcome_1$measure_name[Outcome_1$measure_name=="YLLs (Years of Life Lost)"] <- "YLLs"
list_204c_location_id <- unique(Outcome_1$location_id)
Order_Measure <- c("Deaths", "DALYs", "YLDs", "YLLs")
Order_Disease <- c("Non-communicable diseases", "Cardiovascular diseases", "Chronic respiratory
diseases", "Diabetes and kidney diseases",
                  "Digestive diseases", "Mental disorders", "Musculoskeletal
disorders", "Neurological disorders", "Neoplasms",
                  "Substance use disorders", "Skin and subcutaneous diseases", "Sense organ
diseases")

# 2. Exposure: greenspace
# proxies: annual mean NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index), EVI (Enhanced Vegetation
Index), GS (percentage of greenspace), and TC (percentage of tree cover)
# sources: NDVI and EVI -- MOD13A2 Version 6 product (2000~2021);
#          GS -- MCD12Q1 Version 6.1 product (2001~2021);
#          TC -- MOD44B Version 6 VCF product (2000~2020).
# Notes: (1) The annual mean values of greenspace exposure were calculated using GEE and ArcGIS
10.8.

```

```
# (2) Population-weighted greenspace exposure was calculated using gridded population data
sourced from the Landscan website.
Exposure_1 <- read.csv("Greenspace_2000to2021_204c.csv")
```

```
# 3. Covariates
```

```
# sources: (1) Global Burden of Disease Collaborative Network. Global Burden of Disease Study 2021
(GBD 2021) Covariates 1980-2021. Seattle, United States of America: Institute for Health Metrics and
Evaluation (IHME), 2024.
```

```
# (2) Global Burden of Disease Collaborative Network. Gross Domestic Product Per
Capita 1960-2050. Seattle, United States of America: Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation
(IHME), 2021.
```

```
# (3) Global Burden of Disease Collaborative Network. Global Burden of Disease Study
2021 (GBD 2021) Demographics 1950-2021. Seattle, United States of America: Institute for Health
Metrics and Evaluation (IHME), 2024.
```

```
# (4) World Bank
```

```
# (5) UNdata
```

```
# Integrate all covariate data into a single dataframe:
```

```
# Type 1: Reported for all age and both sexes
```

```
files_tp1 <- list(
```

```
  # urbanicity (%)
```

```
  c("Urbanicity","IHME_GBD_2021_COV_1980_2021_PROP_URBAN_Y2024M04D17.CSV"),
```

```
  # Health expenditure (per capita)
```

```
  c("HealthExpend","IHME_GBD_2021_COV_1980_2021_HE_CAP_Y2024M04D17.CSV"),
```

```
  # Health worker density (per 10,000 population)
```

```
c("HealthWorker","IHME_GBD_2021_COV_1980_2021_HEALTH_WORKER_DENSITY_Y2024
M04D17.CSV"),
```

```
  # vegetable consumption (g/p/d avail unadjusted)
```

```
c("Vegetable","IHME_GBD_2021_COV_1980_2021_VEGETABLES_G_UNADJ_Y2024M04D17.C
SV"),
```

```
  # red meat consumption (g/p/d avail unadjusted)
```

```
c("RedMeat","IHME_GBD_2021_COV_1980_2021_RED_MEATS_G_UNADJ_Y2024M04D17.CS
V"),
```

```
  # alcohol consumption (Liters of alcohol consumed per capita)
```

```
  c("Alcohol","IHME_GBD_2021_COV_1980_2021_LPC_Y2024M04D17.CSV"),
```

```
  # Outdoor Air Pollution (Population weighted PM2.5, micrograms per cubic meter)
```

```
c("PM2.5","IHME_GBD_2021_COV_1980_2021_POLLUTION_OUTDOOR_PM25_Y2024M04D1
7.CSV"),
```

```

# Rainfall Population-Weighted (mm/yr)

c("Rain","IHME_GBD_2021_COV_1980_2021_RAINFALL_POP_WEIGHTED_Y2024M04D17.CSV"),
# Population-weighted mean temperature

c("Temp","IHME_GBD_2021_COV_1980_2021_MEAN_TEMPERATURE_Y2024M04D17.CSV")
)

COV_1 <- unique(Exposure_1[,c("location_id","year")])
for (i in 1:length(files_tp1)) {# i=2
  Label <- files_tp1[[i]][1]
  DataC <- read.csv(files_tp1[[i]][2])
  DataC1 <- DataC[DataC$location_id %in% list_204c_location_id & DataC$year_id %in%
2000:2021 &
                DataC$age_group_name=="All Ages" & DataC$sex == "Both",
                c("location_id","year_id","mean_value")]
  names(DataC1) <- c("location_id","year",Label)
  COV_1 <- merge(COV_1,DataC1,by=c("location_id","year"))
}

# Type 2: Reported by age and by sex
files_tp2 <- list(
  # education level (years/capita)

c("Education","IHME_GBD_2021_COV_1980_2021_EDUCATION_YRS_PC_Y2024M04D17.CSV"),
# smoking prevalence (%)
c("Smoke","IHME_GBD_2021_COV_1980_2021_SMOKING_PREV_Y2024M04D17.CSV")
)

# Population by age and by sex
POP <- read.csv("IHME-GBD_2021_DATA-b7ecd3c2-1.CSV")

for (i in 1:length(files_tp2)){# i=1
  Label <- files_tp2[[i]][1]
  DataC <- read.csv(files_tp2[[i]][2])
  list_2Sex_id <- unique(DataC$sex_id[DataC$sex %in% c("Male","Female")])
  DataC1 <- DataC[DataC$location_id %in% list_204c_location_id & DataC$year_id %in%
2000:2021 &
                DataC$sex_id %in% list_2Sex_id,
                c("location_id","year_id","age_group_id","sex_id","mean_value")]
  names(DataC1) <- c("location_id","year","age_id","sex_id","Cov")
}

```

```

POP1 <- POP[POP$location_id %in% list_204c_location_id & POP$year %in% 2000:2021 &
      POP$sex_id %in% list_2Sex_id & POP$age_id %in%
unique(DataC$age_group_id),
      c("location_id","year","age_id","sex_id","val")]
# convert to estimates of all age and both sexes
DataC2 <- merge(DataC1,POP1); DataC2$multi <- DataC2$Cov*DataC2$val
agg <- aggregate(DataC2$multi, by=list(location_id=DataC2$location_id,year=DataC2$year),
FUN=sum)
POP2 <- POP[POP$location_id %in% list_204c_location_id & POP$year %in% 2000:2021 &
      POP$age_name=="All ages" & POP$sex_name
=="Both",c("location_id","year","val")]
DataC3 <- merge(agg,POP2)
DataC3$COV <- DataC3$x/DataC3$val
DataC3 <- DataC3[,c("location_id","year","COV")]
names(DataC3) <- c("location_id","year",Label)
COV_1 <- merge(COV_1,DataC3,by=c("location_id","year"))
}

# Type 3: Other
# (1) proportion of females (%)
POP_female <- POP[POP$location_id %in% list_204c_location_id & POP$year %in% 2000:2021 &
      POP$sex_name == "Female" & POP$age_name == "All
ages",c("location_id","year","val")]
POP_Both <- POP[POP$location_id %in% list_204c_location_id & POP$year %in% 2000:2021 &
      POP$sex_name == "Both" & POP$age_name == "All
ages",c("location_id","year","val")]
names(POP_female) <- c("location_id","year","Female_num")
names(POP_Both) <- c("location_id","year","Pop_num")
POP_female1 <- merge(POP_female,POP_Both)
POP_female1$FemaleP <- POP_female1$Female_num/POP_female1$Pop_num
COV_1 <-
merge(COV_1,POP_female1[,c("location_id","year","FemaleP","Pop_num")],by=c("location_id","ye
ar"))

# (2) Gross Domestic Product per person (2021 United States Dollars)
GDP <- read.csv("IHME_GDP_1960_2050_Y2023M01D13.CSV")
GDP1 <- GDP[GDP$location_id %in% list_204c_location_id & GDP$year %in%
2000:2021,c("location_id","year","gdp_usd_mean")]
names(GDP1) <- c("location_id","year","GDP")
COV_1 <- merge(COV_1,GDP1,by=c("location_id","year"))

# (3) land area
Land <- read.csv("landarea.csv")

```

```
COV_1 <- merge(COV_1, Land, by=c("location_id", "year"))
```

```
ExpoCov_1 <- merge(Exposure_1, COV_1, all = T)  
summary(is.na(ExpoCov_1)) # check the data
```

```
#####  
## Part 1 Descriptive statistics  
#####
```

```
# Part 1.1 Summary statistics
```

```
# exposure & covariates
```

```
vars_name <- c("NDVI", "EVI", "GS", "TC", "NDVI_popw", "EVI_popw", "GS_popw", "TC_popw",  
              "FemaleP", "GDP", "Urbanicity", "Education", "HealthExpend", "HealthWorker",
```

```
"Vegetable", "RedMeat", "Alcohol", "Smoke", "PM2.5", "Rain", "Temp", "LandArea", "Pop_num")
```

```
vars_label <- c("Annual mean NDVI", "Annual mean EVI", "Annual mean GS (%)", "Annual mean TC  
(%)",
```

```
              "Annual population-weighted mean NDVI", "Annual population-weighted mean  
EVI",
```

```
              "Annual population-weighted mean GS (%)", "Annual population-weighted mean  
TC (%)",
```

```
              "Female (% of total population)", "GDP (dollars/capita)", "Urbanicity (%)",  
              "Education level (years/capita)", "Health expenditure (dollars/capita)",  
              "Health worker density (/10000 population)", "Consumption of vegetables  
(grams/capita/day)",
```

```
              "Consumption of red meat (grams/capita/day)", "Alcohol consumption  
(liters/capita)",
```

```
              "Smoking prevalence (%)", "PM2.5 ( $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ )", "Rainfall (mm)", "Temperature ( $^{\circ}\text{C}$ )",  
              "Land area (square kilometers)", "Population (thousands)")
```

```
vars <- as.data.frame(cbind(vars_name, vars_label))
```

```
vars$vars_order <- 1:nrow(vars)
```

```
for (y in c(2000, 2021)) {
```

```
  des_data <- data.frame()
```

```
  for (i in vars_name) {
```

```
    y1 <- ifelse((y==2000 & i %in% c("GS", "GS_popw")), 2001, ifelse((y==2021 & i %in%  
c("TC", "TC_popw")), 2020, y))
```

```
    datax <- ExpoCov_1[ExpoCov_1$year==y1, ]
```

```
    unit_change <- ifelse(i %in%
```

```
c("FemaleP", "Urbanicity", "Smoke", "GS", "TC", "GS_popw", "TC_popw"), 100, ifelse(i=="Pop_num", 0,
```

```

001,1))
  MEAN <- sprintf("%.2f", mean(datax[,i],na.rm =T)*unit_change)
  SD <- sprintf("%.2f", sd(datax[,i],na.rm =T)*unit_change)
  Min <- sprintf("%.2f", min(datax[,i],na.rm =T)*unit_change)
  Max <- sprintf("%.2f", max(datax[,i],na.rm =T)*unit_change)
  Variable_label <- vars[which(vars$vars_name == i),"vars_label"]
  Variable_order <- vars[which(vars$vars_name == i),"vars_order"]
  Variable_des <- data.frame(Variable_order,Variable_label,MEAN, SD,Min,Max)
  des_data <- rbind(des_data, Variable_des)
}
assign(paste0("des_data_",y),des_data)
}

Descriptive_1 <- merge(des_data_2000,des_data_2021,by=c("Variable_order","Variable_label"))
Descriptive_1 <-
Descriptive_1[order(Descriptive_1$Variable_order),names(Descriptive_1)[!names(Descriptive_1)=="
Variable_order"]]

#outcome
for (y in c(2000,2021)) {
  des_data <- data.frame()
  for (d in Order_Disease) {
    for (m in unique(Outcome_1$measure_name[Outcome_1$cause_name==d])) {
      datax <- Outcome_1[Outcome_1$year==y & Outcome_1$cause_name==d &
Outcome_1$measure_name == m,]
      MEAN <- sprintf("%.2f", mean(datax[, "val"],na.rm =T))
      SD <- sprintf("%.2f", sd(datax[, "val"],na.rm =T))
      Min <- sprintf("%.2f", min(datax[, "val"],na.rm =T))
      Max <- sprintf("%.2f", max(datax[, "val"],na.rm =T))
      Variable_label <- paste0(m," of ",tolower(d)," (/100000)")
      Variable_des <- data.frame(Variable_label,MEAN, SD,Min,Max,d,m)
      des_data <- rbind(des_data, Variable_des)
    }
  }
  assign(paste0("des_data_",y),des_data)
}
Descriptive_2 <- merge(des_data_2000,des_data_2021,by=c("Variable_label","d","m"))
Descriptive_2$d <- factor(Descriptive_2$d,ordered = T,levels = Order_Disease)
Descriptive_2$m <- factor(Descriptive_2$m,ordered = T,levels = Order_Measure)
Descriptive_2 <- Descriptive_2[order(Descriptive_2$d,Descriptive_2$m),names(Descriptive_1)]

Descriptive <- rbind(Descriptive_1,Descriptive_2)
write.csv(Descriptive,paste0(loc_save,"/Table S_Descriptive statistics.csv"),row.names = F)

```

```

# Part 1.2 exploratory graphical analysis
data_label_1 <- ExpoCov_1[ExpoCov_1$year==2010,c("location_id","Pop_num","GDP")]
data_label_1$pop_c <- cut(data_label_1$Pop_num,
                        breaks = c(-Inf, 5000000, 50000000, Inf),
                        labels = c("<5 million", "5-50 million", "≥50 million"),
                        right = FALSE)
data_label_1$GDP_c <- cut(data_label_1$GDP,
                        breaks =
c(-Inf,quantile(data_label_1$GDP, .20),quantile(data_label_1$GDP, .40),quantile(data_label_1$GDP, .
60),quantile(data_label_1$GDP, .80),Inf),
                        labels = c("Q1 (lowest)","Q2","Q3","Q4","Q5 (highest)"),
                        right = FALSE)

dataxy_within_all <- data.frame()
data_lm <- data.frame()
library(dplyr)
for (x in c("NDVI","EVI","GS","TC")) {
  for (m in c("Deaths","DALYs")) {
    datax <- ExpoCov_1[,c("location_id","year",x,"LandArea")]
    datay <- Outcome_1[Outcome_1$cause_name=="Non-communicable diseases" &
                      Outcome_1$measure_name ==m, c("location_id","year","val")]
    dataxy <- merge(datax,datay,by=c("location_id","year"))
    names(dataxy) <- c("location_id","year","x","LandArea","y")

#median centering
dataxy_within <- dataxy %>%
  group_by(location_id) %>%
  mutate(x_within = x - median(x, na.rm = TRUE),
         y_within = y - median(y, na.rm = TRUE)) %>%
  ungroup()
dataxy_within <- merge(dataxy_within,data_label_1)

dataxy_within$Exposure <-x
dataxy_within$measure <-m
dataxy_within_all <- rbind(dataxy_within_all,dataxy_within)

outlier_x_l <-quantile(dataxy_within$x_within,0.025,na.rm=T)
outlier_x_h <-quantile(dataxy_within$x_within,0.975,na.rm=T)
outlier_y_l <-quantile(dataxy_within$y_within,0.025,na.rm=T)
outlier_y_h <-quantile(dataxy_within$y_within,0.975,na.rm=T)
dataxy_within_rm <- dataxy_within[which(dataxy_within$x_within > outlier_x_l &
                                       dataxy_within$x_within < outlier_x_h &
                                       dataxy_within$y_within > outlier_y_l &

```

```
dataxy_within$y_within < outlier_y_h,]
```

```
dataxy_within <- na.omit(dataxy_within)
model_lm <- lm(y_within ~ x_within, data = dataxy_within)
Coef <- as.data.frame(summary(model_lm)$coefficients)

# check the outlier
#dataxy_within$cook_distance <- cooks.distance(model_lm)
#threshold <- 4 / (nrow(dataxy_within)-model_lm$rank)
#outlier_data <- dataxy_within[dataxy_within$cook_distance > threshold,]
#outlier_data <- outlier_data[order(outlier_data$cook_distance,decreasing = T),]
#print(unique(Outcome_1$location_name[Outcome_1$location_id %in%
outlier_data$location_id[1:3]]))

#sen1
dataxy_within_rm <- na.omit(dataxy_within_rm)
model_lm_rm <- lm(y_within ~ x_within, data = dataxy_within_rm)
Coef_rm <- as.data.frame(summary(model_lm_rm)$coefficients)

#sen2
model_lm_w <- lm(y_within ~ x_within, data = dataxy_within,weights = LandArea)
Coef_w <- as.data.frame(summary(model_lm_w)$coefficients)

data_lm1 <- data.frame(Exposure=x,measure=m,
                      Estimate =
sprintf("%.2f",Coef$Estimate[row.names(Coef)=="x_within"]),
                      SE = sprintf("%.4f",Coef$`Std.
Error`[row.names(Coef)=="x_within"]),
                      t= sprintf("%.2f",Coef$t value`[row.names(Coef)=="x_within"]),
                      P= sprintf("%.4f",Coef$`Pr(>|t|)`[row.names(Coef)=="x_within"]),

                      Estimate_rm =
sprintf("%.2f",Coef_rm$Estimate[row.names(Coef_rm)=="x_within"]),
                      SE_rm = sprintf("%.4f",Coef_rm$`Std.
Error`[row.names(Coef_rm)=="x_within"]),
                      t= sprintf("%.2f",Coef_rm$t
value`[row.names(Coef_rm)=="x_within"]),

                      P_rm=sprintf("%.4f",Coef_rm$`Pr(>|t|)`[row.names(Coef_rm)=="x_within"]),

                      Estimate_w =
sprintf("%.2f",Coef_w$Estimate[row.names(Coef_w)=="x_within"]),
                      SE_w = sprintf("%.4f",Coef_w$`Std.
Error`[row.names(Coef_w)=="x_within"]),
```

```

t= sprintf("%.2f",Coef_w$t
value`[row.names(Coef_w)== "x_within"]),

P_w=sprintf("%.4f",Coef_w$`Pr(>|t|)`[row.names(Coef_w)== "x_within"])
)
data_lm <- rbind(data_lm,data_lm1)
}}

data_lm$P <- ifelse(data_lm$P<0.0001,"<0.0001",data_lm$P)
data_lm$P_rm <- ifelse(data_lm$P_rm<0.0001,"<0.0001",data_lm$P_rm)
data_lm$P_w <- ifelse(data_lm$P_w<0.0001,"<0.0001",data_lm$P_w)

write.csv(data_lm,paste0(loc_save,"/Table S_scatter plot.csv"),row.names = F)

library(ggplot2)
library(RColorBrewer)
library(grid)
color_R = brewer.pal(n= 5, name = "PRGn")
cols <- c("Q1 (lowest)" = color_R[1],
          "Q2" = color_R[2],
          "Q3" = color_R[3],
          "Q4" = color_R[4],
          "Q5 (highest)" = color_R[5])

dataxy_within_all$Exposure <- factor(dataxy_within_all$Exposure,ordered = T,levels =
c("NDVI","EVI","GS","TC"))
dataxy_within_all$measure <- factor(dataxy_within_all$measure,ordered = T,levels =
c("Deaths",'DALYs'))
names(dataxy_within_all)[names(dataxy_within_all)== "pop_c"] <- "Population (2010)"
names(dataxy_within_all)[names(dataxy_within_all)== "GDP_c"] <- "GDP quintile (2010)"

p <- ggplot(data = dataxy_within_all,aes(x = x_within, y = y_within))+
geom_point(data = dataxy_within_all, aes(x_within, y = y_within,
colour=`GDP quintile (2010)`,size = `Population
(2010)`, alpha = 0.0001)) +
scale_color_manual(values = cols, aesthetics = c("colour", "fill"),na.value = "grey90")+
guides(`GDP quintile (2010)` = T, `Population (2010)` = T, alpha = F,
color=guide_legend(override.aes = list(size=4,alpha=0.8)))+
coord_cartesian() +
geom_smooth(method = "lm",formula = y~x, size= 0.5, colour= "#4D6A75",
alpha = 0.2, linetype = "solid")+
geom_vline(xintercept = 0, color = "#4D6A75",size= 0.5,linetype="dashed")+
geom_hline(yintercept = 0, color = "#4D6A75",size= 0.5,linetype="dashed")+

```

```

xlab("Median-centered greenspace") +
ylab("Median-centered disease burden of NCDs(/100 000)")+
facet_grid(measure~ Exposure, scales = "free") +
theme_bw() +
theme(panel.spacing = unit(1, "lines"),
      text=element_text(size=24, color="black", family = "serif"),
      plot.margin = margin(t = 20, r = 20, b = 30, l = 30),
      legend.title = element_text(size = 22, family = "serif", color = "black"),
      legend.text = element_text(size = 22, family = "serif", color = "black"),
      strip.text = element_text(size = 24, color = "black", family = "serif", face = "bold"),
      axis.text = element_text(size=18, color="black", family = "serif"),
      axis.title = element_text(size=24, color="black", family = "serif", face = "bold"),
      axis.title.x = element_text(vjust = -1),
      axis.title.y = element_text(vjust = 1),
      legend.position = "right",
      legend.direction = "vertical",
      legend.key = element_rect(fill = "grey90"),
      plot.title = element_text(color="black", size=24, family = "serif",
                                face = "bold", hjust = -0.15, vjust = -0.5))

p1 <- p + annotation_custom(
  grob = grobTree(
    textGrob("P", x = unit(0.1, "npc"), y = unit(0.8, "npc"),
             gp = gpar(col = "black", fontsize = 18, fontfamily = "serif", fontface = "italic")),
    textGrob("< 0.0001", x = unit(0.26, "npc"), y = unit(0.8, "npc"),
             gp = gpar(col = "black", fontsize = 18, fontfamily = "serif"))))

ggsave(file = paste0(loc_save, "/Figure 1_scatter.pdf"), plot = p1, width = 21, height = 9, device =
cairo_pdf)

#####
## Part 2 Associations between greenspace and NCDs-related disease burden
#####

# Part 2.1 Spatial correlation
library(sf)
library(spdep)
library(data.table)
#Note: The maps used in this study are for academic research purposes only and do not represent any
political stance.
Map <- sf::st_read(paste0(loc_file, "/map/Map_global.shp"))

```

```

Map <- Map[,c("loctn_d", "geometry")]
names(Map)[1] <- "location_id"
Map_1 <- Map[Map$location_id %in% list_204c_location_id,]
neighbors <- poly2nb(Map_1, queen=T, snap = 0.001)
listw <- nb2listw(neighbors, style = "W", zero.policy=T)

data_moran <- data.frame()
Outcome_Map <- merge(Outcome_1, Map_1)
for (y in 2000:2021) {
  for (d in Order_Disease) {
    for (m in unique(Outcome_Map$measure_name[Outcome_Map$cause_name==d])) {
      Outcome_Map_x <- Outcome_Map[Outcome_Map$year==y &
Outcome_Map$measure_name == m & Outcome_Map$cause_name == d,]
      moran_result <- moran.test(Outcome_Map_x$val, listw=listw)
      moran_stat <- as.numeric(moran_result$estimate["Moran I statistic"])
      moran_p <- as.numeric(moran_result$p.value)
      datax <- data.frame(year=y, measure_name=m, cause_name=d, moran_stat, moran_p)
      data_moran <- rbind(data_moran, datax)
    }
  }
}

nrow(data_moran[data_moran$moran_p<0.05,])/nrow(data_moran)
summary(data_moran$moran_stat[data_moran$moran_p<0.05])
#85%: mild positive spatial autocorrelation (0.10~0.39)

#Spatially lagged variable (weighted averages of observations for the “neighbours” of a given
location)
Outcome_Map_1 <- data.frame()
for (y in 2000:2021) { # y=2000;m="Deaths";d="Non-communicable diseases"
  for (d in Order_Disease) {
    for (m in unique(Outcome_Map$measure_name[Outcome_Map$cause_name==d])) {
      Outcome_Map_x <- Outcome_Map[Outcome_Map$year==y &
Outcome_Map$measure_name == m & Outcome_Map$cause_name == d,]
      Outcome_Map_x$SpaLag_val <- lag.listw(listw, Outcome_Map_x$val)
      Outcome_Map_1 <-
rbind(Outcome_Map_1, Outcome_Map_x[,names(Outcome_Map_x)[!names(Outcome_Map_x)%in%"
geometry" ]])
    }
  }
}

# Part 2.2 DAG
library(dagitty)
library(lavaan)
cov_candidate <-

```

```
c("Urbanicity","HealthExpend","HealthWorker","Vegetable","RedMeat","Alcohol","PM2.5",
  "Rain","Temp","Education","Smoke","FemaleP","GDP")
```

```
cov_label <- c("Urbanicity","Health expenditure","Health worker density",
  "Vegetable consumption","Red meat consumption","Alcohol consumption",
  "Ambient air pollution","Rainfall","Temperature","Education","Smoking
prevalence",
  "Proportion of females","GDP")
```

```
covs <- as.data.frame(cbind(cov_candidate,cov_label))
cov_label <- setNames(covs$cov_label, covs$cov_candidate)
```

```
# the original DAG
```

```
g1 <- downloadGraph("dagitty.net/mYdCBZkio")
```

```
fun_cov_cat_0 <- function(data,var_name){
  data <- data %>%
    mutate(var_xc = case_when(
      data[,var_name] < quantile(data[,var_name],.20) ~ "1",
      data[,var_name] >= quantile(data[,var_name],.20) & data[,var_name] <
quantile(data[,var_name],.40) ~ "2",
      data[,var_name] >= quantile(data[,var_name],.40) & data[,var_name] <
quantile(data[,var_name],.60) ~ "3",
      data[,var_name] >= quantile(data[,var_name],.60) & data[,var_name] <
quantile(data[,var_name],.80) ~ "4",
      data[,var_name] >= quantile(data[,var_name],.80) ~ "5"
    ))
  data$var_xc <- factor(data$var_xc)
  data <- data[,names(data)[!names(data)%in%var_name]]
  names(data)[names(data)=="var_xc"] <- var_name
  data[,var_name] <- as.integer(data[,var_name])
  return(data)
}
```

```
fun_testDAG <- function(g,p,m){
  data1 <- ExpoCov_1; names(data1)[names(data1)==p] <- "Greenspace"
  data1 <- data1[,c("location_id","year","Greenspace",cov_candidate)]
  data2 <- Outcome_1[Outcome_1$measure_name==m & Outcome_1$cause_name ==
"Non-communicable diseases",c("location_id","year","val")]
  names(data2)[3] <- "NCDs"
  d <- merge(data1,data2)
  if(x %in% c("GS","TC")){d <- na.omit(d)}

  d$NCDs <- log10(d$NCDs)
```

```

d <- d %>%
  group_by(location_id) %>%
  mutate(across(c(names(d)[!names(d)%in% c("location_id","year")]), ~ . - median(., na.rm =
TRUE))) %>%
  ungroup()
d <- as.data.frame(d)
for (c in cov_candidate) {d <- fun_cov_cat_0(d,c)}

corr <- lavCor(d[,names(d)[!names(d) %in% c("location_id","year")]])

r<-localTests(g,d,sample.cov=corr,sample.nobs=nrow(d),max.conditioning.variables=2,abbreviate.names = F)

r$p.value<-p.adjust(r$p.value)#corrected for multiple testing
r <- r[order(r$estimate),]
return(r)
}

r1 <- fun_testDAG(g=g1,p="NDVI",m="Deaths")

new_row_names <- sapply(row.names(r1), function(rn) {
  tokens <- strsplit(rn, "(?<=[^\\w.])|(?!=[^\\w.])", perl = TRUE)[[1]]
  replaced_tokens <- sapply(tokens, function(token) {
    if (token %in% names(cov_label)) {
      cov_label[[token]]
    } else {
      token
    }
  })
  paste(replaced_tokens, collapse = "")
})
row.names(r1) <- new_row_names

pdf(paste0(loc_save,"/Figure S_DAG_test1.pdf"), width = 12, height = 8, family = "serif")
par(cex.axis = 1,cex.lab = 1,cex.main = 1)
plotLocalTestResults(r1, xlab = "partial correlation (95% CI)")
dev.off()
adjustmentSets(g1,exposure="Greenspace",outcome="NCDs",type = "minimal",effect="total")

r1$Simply <- row.names(r1)
r1$P <- sprintf("%.4f",r1$p.value)
r1$Corre <- paste0(sprintf("%.2f",r1$estimate)," (",sprintf("%.2f",r1$`2.5%`),"

```

```

",sprintf("%.2f",r1$`97.5%`,`),")")
r1 <- r1[order(r1$estimate,decreasing =T),]
r1_1 <- r1[,c("imply","corre","P")]
r1_1$P[r1_1$P == "0.0000"] <- "<0.0001"
names(r1_1) <- c("Implied conditional independencies", "Partial correlation (95% CI)","P")
write.csv(r1_1,paste0(loc_save,"/Table S_validate_DAG1.csv"),row.names = F)

g2 <- downloadGraph("dagitty.net/mKEMjwAJx")

r2 <- fun_testDAG(g=g2,p="NDVI",m="Deaths")

new_row_names <- sapply(row.names(r2), function(rn) {
  tokens <- strsplit(rn, "(?<=[^\\w.])|(?!=[^\\w.])", perl = TRUE)[[1]]
  replaced_tokens <- sapply(tokens, function(token) {
    if(token %in% names(cov_label)) {
      cov_label[[token]]
    } else {
      token
    }
  })
  paste(replaced_tokens, collapse = "")
})
row.names(r2) <- new_row_names

pdf(paste0(loc_save,"/Figure S_DAG_test2.pdf"), width = 12, height = 7, family = "serif")
par(cex.axis = 1,cex.lab = 1,cex.main = 1)
plotLocalTestResults(r2, xlab = "partial correlation (95% CI)")
dev.off()
adjustmentSets(g2,exposure="Greenspace",outcome="NCDs",type = "minimal",effect="total")

r1$imply <- row.names(r1)
r1$P <- sprintf("%.4f",r1$p.value)
r1$corre <- paste0(sprintf("%.2f",r1$estimate)," (",sprintf("%.2f",r1$`2.5%`,`),",",
",sprintf("%.2f",r1$`97.5%`,`),")")
r1 <- r1[order(r1$estimate,decreasing =T),]
r1_1 <- r1[,c("imply","corre","P")]
r1_1$P[r1_1$P == "0.0000"] <- "<0.0001"
names(r1_1) <- c("Implied conditional independencies", "Partial correlation (95% CI)","P")
write.csv(r1_1,paste0(loc_save,"/Table S_validate_DAG1.csv"),row.names = F)

r2$imply <- row.names(r2)
r2$P <- sprintf("%.4f",r2$p.value)

```

```

r2$corre <- paste0(sprintf("%.2f",r2$estimate)," (",sprintf("%.2f",r2$`2.5%`),"",
",sprintf("%.2f",r2$`97.5%`),")")
r2 <- r2[order(r2$estimate,decreasing =T),]
r2_1 <- r2[,c("imply","corre","P")]
r2_1$P[r2_1$P == "0.0000"] <- "<0.0001"
names(r2_1) <- c("Implied conditional independencies", "Partial correlation (95% CI)","P")
write.csv(r2_1,paste0(loc_save,"/Table S_validate_DAG2.csv"),row.names = F)

```

```

COV_list <- c("Education", "FemaleP", "GDP", "Rain", "Urbanicity", "SpaLag_val")

```

```

# Part 2.3 Nonlinear analysis

```

```

library(nlme)
library(dplyr)
library(ggplot2)
library(rms)

```

```

fun_cov_cat <- function(data,var_name){
  data <- data %>%
    mutate(var_xc = case_when(
      data[,var_name] < quantile(data[,var_name],.20) ~ "1",
      data[,var_name] >= quantile(data[,var_name],.20) & data[,var_name] <
quantile(data[,var_name],.40) ~ "2",
      data[,var_name] >= quantile(data[,var_name],.40) & data[,var_name] <
quantile(data[,var_name],.60) ~ "3",
      data[,var_name] >= quantile(data[,var_name],.60) & data[,var_name] <
quantile(data[,var_name],.80) ~ "4",
      data[,var_name] >= quantile(data[,var_name],.80) ~ "5"
    ))
  data$var_xc <- factor(data$var_xc)
  names(data)[names(data)=="var_xc"] <- paste0(var_name,"_c")
  return(data)
}
COV_list_c <- paste0(COV_list,"_c")

```

```

Outcome_Map_1$measure_name <- factor(Outcome_Map_1$measure_name,ordered = T,levels =
Order_Measure)
Outcome_Map_1$cause_name <- factor(Outcome_Map_1$cause_name,ordered = T,levels =
Order_Disease)
Outcome_Map_1 <-
Outcome_Map_1[order(Outcome_Map_1$cause_name,Outcome_Map_1$measure_name),]

```

```

Judge_Nonlinear <- data.frame()
for (y1 in Order_Disease) {
  for (y2 in unique(Outcome_Map_1$measure_name[Outcome_Map_1$cause_name==y1])) {
    for (x in c("NDVI","EVI","GS","TC")) {
      # y1="Non-communicable diseases";y2="Deaths";x="NDVI"
      #merge data
      datax <- ExpoCov_1
      datay <- Outcome_Map_1 [Outcome_Map_1$cause_name==y1 & Outcome_Map_1
$measure_name==y2,c("location_id","year","val","SpaLag_val")]
      data_all <- merge(datax,datay,all = T)
      if(x %in% c("GS","TC")){data_all <- na.omit(data_all)}
      for (c in COV_list) {data_all <- fun_cov_cat(data_all,c)}

      data_all <- fun_cov_cat(data_all,"LandArea")
      data_all$LandArea_c <- as.integer(data_all$LandArea_c)
      data_all$weights <- data_all[, "LandArea_c"]

      #formula of covariate
      form_c <- paste0(COV_list_c[1])
      for (c in 2:length(COV_list_c)) {form_c <- paste0(form_c,"+",COV_list_c[c])}

      #compare linear and Non-linear models: P, AIC, BIC
      chooseAIC <- data.frame()
      for(k in 3:7){
        dd <- datadist(data_all)
        options(datadist='dd')
        model1 <- lme(as.formula(paste0("log10(val) ~ rcs(",x,"",k,")+",form_c)),
                    random = ~ 1| location_id, data=data_all,method = "ML",
                    correlation = corAR1(form = ~ 1| location_id),
                    weights = varFixed(~weights),
                    control = lmeControl(opt = "optim", tolerance = 1e-4, maxIter = 5000,
msMaxIter = 5000))
        aic <- AIC(model1); chooseAIC_1 <- cbind(k, aic)
        chooseAIC <- rbind(chooseAIC, chooseAIC_1)
      }
      k_min <- chooseAIC$k[chooseAIC$aic == min(chooseAIC$aic)]

      dd <- datadist(data_all)
      options(datadist='dd')
      model_nonlinear<- lme(as.formula(paste0("log10(val) ~ rcs(",x,"",k_min,")+",form_c)),
                          random = ~ 1| location_id, data=data_all,method = "ML",
                          correlation = corAR1(form = ~ 1| location_id),
                          weights = varFixed(~weights),
                          control = lmeControl(opt = "optim", tolerance = 1e-4, maxIter =

```

```

5000, msMaxIter = 5000))
  model_linear <- lme(as.formula(paste0("log10(val) ~ ",x,"+",form_c)),
    random = ~ 1| location_id, data_all,
    correlation = corAR1(form = ~ 1| location_id),method = "ML",
    weights = varFixed(~weights),
    control = lmeControl(opt = "optim", tolerance = 1e-4, maxIter = 5000,
msMaxIter = 5000))
  anova_2m <- anova(model_linear, model_nonlinear)
  P_anova <- anova_2m$p-value[2]
  AIC_linear <- anova_2m$AIC[row.names(anova_2m)=="model_linear"]
  BIC_linear <- anova_2m$BIC[row.names(anova_2m)=="model_linear"]
  AIC_nonlinear <- anova_2m$AIC[row.names(anova_2m)=="model_nonlinear"]
  BIC_nonlinear <- anova_2m$BIC[row.names(anova_2m)=="model_nonlinear"]
  Judge_1 <- data.frame(Outcome=y1,measure=y2,Exposure=x,
    AIC_linear,BIC_linear,AIC_nonlinear,BIC_nonlinear,P_anova)
  Judge_Nonlinear <- rbind(Judge_Nonlinear,Judge_1)
  }}}

Judge_Nonlinear$P_anova <-
ifelse(Judge_Nonlinear$P_anova<0.0001,"<0.0001",Judge_Nonlinear$P_anova)
write.csv(Judge_Nonlinear,paste0(loc_save,"/Table S_Judge_Nonlinear.csv"),row.names = F)

```

Part 2.4 Main analysis: crude and adjusted models

```

fun_nonline_2Q <- function(data,var_name){ #data=data_all;var_name="Education"
  data <- data %>%
    mutate(var_xc = case_when(
      data[,var_name] < quantile(data[,var_name],.50) ~ "1",
      data[,var_name] >= quantile(data[,var_name],.50) ~ "2"
    ))
  data$var_xc <- factor(data$var_xc)
  names(data)[names(data)=="var_xc"] <- paste0(var_name,"_c")
  return(data)
}

library(car)
fun_model_weight <- function(data,x,y,cov,var_w){ #
data=data_all;x="EVI";y="val";cov=COV_list_c;var_w="LandArea_c"
#crude model
formula1 <- paste0("log10(",y,") ~ ",x)
#adjusted model
if(length(cov)!=0){for (c in 1:length(cov)) {formula1 <- paste0(formula1,"+",cov[c])}}
}

```

```

data$weights <- data[,var_w]
model_linear <- lme(as.formula(formula1),data,
                    random = ~ 1| location_name,
                    correlation = corAR1(form = ~ 1| location_name),
                    method = "ML",
                    weights = varFixed(~weights),
                    control = lmeControl(opt = "nlminb", tolerance = 1e-4, maxIter = 5000,
msMaxIter = 5000))
coef <- summary(model_linear)$tTable
ci <- intervals(model_linear, level = 0.95, which = "fixed")

if(class(data[,x])=="numeric"){
  VIF_max <-
ifelse(length(cov)==0,NA,max(as.data.frame(vif(model_linear))$`GVIF^(1/(2*Df))`))
  Beta_raw_m <- coef[x,"Value"]
  Beta_raw_l <- ci[x,"lower"]
  Beta_raw_u <- ci[x,"upper"]
  Beta_m <- (10^(0.1*coef[x,"Value"])-1)*100
  Beta_l <- (10^(0.1*ci[x,"lower"])-1)*100
  Beta_u <- (10^(0.1*ci[x,"upper"])-1)*100
  Beta <- paste(sprintf("%.2f",Beta_m)," (", sprintf("%.2f",Beta_l), ", ", sprintf("%.2f",Beta_u),
"),sep = "")
  P_value <- coef[x,"p-value"];P <- ifelse(P_value<0.0001,"<0.0001",sprintf("%.4f",P_value))
  SE_value <- coef[x,"Std.Error"];SE <- sprintf("%.4f",SE_value)
  result <-
data.frame(Q="/",Beta,P,SE,Beta_m,Beta_l,Beta_u,Beta_raw_m,Beta_raw_l,Beta_raw_u,P_value,SE_
value,VIF_max,formula1)

}else{
  x_c <- c(paste0(x,"2"))
  VIF_max <-
ifelse(length(cov)==0,NA,max(as.data.frame(vif(model_linear))$`GVIF^(1/(2*Df))`))
  Beta_raw_m <- coef[x_c,"Value"]
  Beta_raw_l <- ci[x_c,"lower"]
  Beta_raw_u <- ci[x_c,"upper"]
  Beta_m <- (10^(coef[x_c,"Value"])-1)*100
  Beta_l <- (10^(ci[x_c,"lower"])-1)*100
  Beta_u <- (10^(ci[x_c,"upper"])-1)*100
  P_value <- coef[x_c,"p-value"]
  SE_value <- coef[x_c,"Std.Error"]
  result <-
data.frame(Q=c("Q2"),Beta_m,Beta_l,Beta_u,Beta_raw_m,Beta_raw_l,Beta_raw_u,P_value,SE_value,
VIF_max,formula1)
  result$Beta <- paste(sprintf("%.2f",result$Beta_m)," (", sprintf("%.2f",result$Beta_l), ", ",

```

```

sprintf("%.2f",result$Beta_u, ")",sep = "")
  result$P <- ifelse(result$P_value<0.0001,"<0.0001",sprintf("%.4f",result$P_value))
  result$SE <- sprintf("%.4f",result$SE_value)
  result <-
result[,c("Q","Beta","P","SE","Beta_m","Beta_l","Beta_u","Beta_raw_m","Beta_raw_l","Beta_raw_u
","P_value","SE_value","VIF_max","formula1")]
  }
  return(result)
}

```

```

result_crude <- data.frame()
result_main <- data.frame()
for (y1 in Order_Disease) {
  for (y2 in unique(Outcome_Map_1$measure_name[Outcome_Map_1$cause_name==y1])) {
    for (x in c("NDVI","EVI","GS","TC")) {
      #merge data
      datax <- ExpoCov_1
      datay <- Outcome_Map_1[Outcome_Map_1$cause_name==y1 &
Outcome_Map_1$measure_name==y2,c("location_id","location_name","year","val","SpaLag_val")]
      data_all <- merge(datax,datay,all = T)

      if(x %in% c("GS","TC")){data_all <- na.omit(data_all)}
      for (c in c(COV_list)) {data_all <- fun_cov_cat(data_all,c)}

      data_all <- fun_cov_cat(data_all,"LandArea")
      data_all$LandArea_c <- as.integer(data_all$LandArea_c)

      if(y2 == "YLDs"){x_1 <- paste0(x,"_c");data_all <- fun_nonline_2Q(data_all,x)}else{x_1 <-
x}

      result_crude1 <- cbind(Outcome=y1,
measure=y2,Exposure=x,fun_model_weight(data=data_all,x=x_1,y="val",cov =
NULL,var_w="LandArea_c"))
      result_main1 <- cbind(Outcome=y1,
measure=y2,Exposure=x,fun_model_weight(data=data_all,x=x_1,y="val",cov =
COV_list_c,var_w="LandArea_c"))

      result_crude <- rbind(result_crude,result_crude1)
      result_main <- rbind(result_main,result_main1)
    }
  }
}

```

```

result_crude$Model <- "Crude"
result_main$Model <- "Adjusted"
result_crude_main <- rbind(result_crude,result_main)

```

```

result_crude_main$Exposure <- factor(result_crude_main$Exposure,ordered = T,levels =
c("NDVI","EVI","GS","TC"))
result_crude_main$Outcome <- factor(result_crude_main$Outcome,ordered = T,levels =
Order_Disease)
result_crude_main$measure <- factor(result_crude_main$measure,ordered = T,levels =
Order_Measure)
result_crude_main$Model <- factor(result_crude_main$Model,ordered = T,levels =
c("Crude","Adjusted"))
result_crude_main <-
result_crude_main[order(result_crude_main$Model,result_crude_main$Outcome,

result_crude_main$measure,result_crude_main$Exposure),]
result_crude_main <-
result_crude_main[,c("Outcome","measure","Exposure","Q","Beta","P","SE","Model")]
names(result_crude_main) <- c("Disease","Index","Greenspace","Quintile","Estimate (95%
CI)","P","SE","Model")

write.csv(result_crude_main,paste0(loc_save,"/Table S_Crude and adjusted
associations.csv"),row.names = F)

df <- result_main
df$PP <- ifelse(df$P_value < 0.05,"*"," ")
df$Exposure <- factor(df$Exposure,ordered = T,levels = c("NDVI","EVI","GS","TC"))

mytheme <- theme_bw()+
  theme(text=element_text(size=26, color="black", family = "serif"),
        axis.text = element_text(size=26, color="black", family = "serif"),
        axis.title.x = element_text(vjust = -1, face ="bold"),
        panel.spacing = unit(1, "lines"),
        plot.margin = margin(t = 20, r = 20, b = 20, l = 20),
        strip.text.x = element_text(size = 26, color = "black", face = "bold"),
        panel.grid.major = element_line(colour = "grey95", size = 0.1),
        panel.grid.minor = element_line(colour = "grey95", size = 0.1))

p1 <- ggplot(data = df[df$measure == "Deaths",])+geom_point(size = 4, shape = 18, aes(x=Beta_m,
y= Outcome))+
  geom_errorbarh(aes(y=Outcome,xmin=Beta_l,xmax=Beta_u),height = 0.4, alpha=1.0, size = 0.3)+
  geom_vline(xintercept = 0, color = "black",linetype="dashed",alpha=1.0, size =0.1)+
  labs(x= "Estimate (95% CI)",y=NULL,size=30)+
  geom_text(aes(label = PP, x=Beta_l-0.3, y= Outcome),
            vjust='center', size = 8, show.legend = F, nudge_y = -0.1, alpha=0.8)+
  facet_wrap(Exposure ~., ncol=2)+
  scale_y_discrete(limits = rev(c(Order_Disease)))+
  mytheme

```

```

p2 <- ggplot(data = df[df$measure == "DALYs",])+geom_point(size = 4, shape = 18, aes(x=Beta_m,
y= Outcome))+
  geom_errorbarh(aes(y=Outcome,xmin=Beta_l,xmax=Beta_u),height = 0.4, alpha=1.0, size = 0.3)+
  geom_vline(xintercept = 0, color = "black",linetype="dashed",alpha=1.0, size =0.1)+
  labs(x= "Estimate (95% CI)",y=NULL,size=30)+
  geom_text(aes(label = PP, x=Beta_l-0.3, y= Outcome),
            vjust='center', size = 8, show.legend = F, nudge_y = -0.1, alpha=0.8)+
  facet_wrap(Exposure ~., ncol=2)+
  scale_y_discrete(limits = rev(c(Order_Disease)))+
  mytheme

```

```

p3 <- ggplot(data = df[df$measure == "YLDs",])+geom_point(size = 4, shape = 18, aes(x=Beta_m, y=
Outcome))+
  geom_errorbarh(aes(y=Outcome,xmin=Beta_l,xmax=Beta_u),height = 0.4, alpha=1.0, size = 0.3)+
  geom_vline(xintercept = 0, color = "black",linetype="dashed",alpha=1.0, size =0.1)+
  labs(x= "Estimate (95% CI)",y=NULL,size=30)+
  geom_text(aes(label = PP, x=Beta_l-0.3, y= Outcome),
            vjust='center', size = 8, show.legend = F, nudge_y = -0.1, alpha=0.8)+
  facet_wrap(Exposure ~., ncol=2)+
  scale_y_discrete(limits = rev(c(Order_Disease)))+
  mytheme

```

```

p4 <- ggplot(data = df[df$measure == "YLLs",])+geom_point(size = 4, shape = 18, aes(x=Beta_m, y=
Outcome))+
  geom_errorbarh(aes(y=Outcome,xmin=Beta_l,xmax=Beta_u),height = 0.4, alpha=1.0, size = 0.3)+
  geom_vline(xintercept = 0, color = "black",linetype="dashed",alpha=1.0, size =0.1)+
  labs(x= "Estimate (95% CI)",y=NULL,size=30)+
  geom_text(aes(label = PP, x=Beta_l-0.3, y= Outcome),
            vjust='center', size = 8, show.legend = F, nudge_y = -0.1, alpha=0.8)+
  facet_wrap(Exposure ~., ncol=2)+
  scale_y_discrete(limits = rev(c(Order_Disease)))+
  mytheme

```

```

ggsave(file = paste0(loc_save,"/Figure 2_Adjusted_deaths.pdf"), plot = p1, width = 13, height = 12)
ggsave(file = paste0(loc_save,"/Figure 3_Adjusted_DALYs.pdf"), plot = p2, width = 13, height = 12)
ggsave(file = paste0(loc_save,"/Figure S_Adjusted_YLDs.pdf"), plot = p3, width = 13, height = 12)
ggsave(file = paste0(loc_save,"/Figure S_Adjusted_YLLs.pdf"), plot = p4, width = 13, height = 12)

```

```

# Part 2.5 Sensitivity analysis
result_sen1 <- data.frame()
result_sen2 <- data.frame()

```

```

result_sen3 <- data.frame()
result_sen4 <- data.frame()
result_sen5 <- data.frame()
result_sen6 <- data.frame()
result_sen7 <- data.frame()
result_sen8 <- data.frame()

fun_model_weight_SCMMs <- function(data,x,y,cov,var_w){
  #crude model
  formula1 <- paste0("log10(",y,") ~ ",x,"+x_lag1")
  #adjusted model
  if(length(cov)!=0){for (c in 1:length(cov)) {formula1 <- paste0(formula1,"+",cov[c])}}

  data$weights <- data[,var_w]
  model_linear <- lme(as.formula(formula1),data,
                    random = ~ 1| location_name,
                    correlation = corAR1(form = ~ 1| location_name),
                    method = "ML",
                    weights = varFixed(~weights),
                    na.action = na.exclude,
                    control = lmeControl(opt = "nlminb", tolerance = 1e-4, maxIter = 5000,
msMaxIter = 5000))
  coef <- summary(model_linear)$tTable
  ci <- intervals(model_linear, level = 0.95, which = "fixed")

  if(class(data[,x])=="numeric"){
    VIF_max <-
ifelse(length(cov)==0,NA,max(as.data.frame(vif(model_linear))$`GVIF^(1/(2*Df))`))
    Beta_raw_m <- coef[x,"Value"]
    Beta_raw_l <- ci[x,"lower"]
    Beta_raw_u <- ci[x,"upper"]
    Beta_m <- (10^(0.1*coef[x,"Value"])-1)*100
    Beta_l <- (10^(0.1*ci[x,"lower"])-1)*100
    Beta_u <- (10^(0.1*ci[x,"upper"])-1)*100
    Beta <- paste(sprintf("%.2f",Beta_m), " (", sprintf("%.2f",Beta_l), ", ", sprintf("%.2f",Beta_u),
    ")",sep = "")
    P_value <- coef[x,"p-value"];P <- ifelse(P_value<0.0001,"<0.0001",sprintf("%.4f",P_value))
    SE_value <- coef[x,"Std.Error"];SE <- sprintf("%.4f",SE_value)
    result <-
data.frame(Q="/",Beta,P,SE,Beta_m,Beta_l,Beta_u,Beta_raw_m,Beta_raw_l,Beta_raw_u,P_value,SE_
value,VIF_max,formula1)

  }else{
    x_c <- c(paste0(x,"2"))

```

```

VIF_max <-
ifelse(length(cov)==0,NA,max(as.data.frame(vif(model_linear))$`GVIF^(1/(2*Df))`))
  Beta_raw_m <- coef[x_c,"Value"]
  Beta_raw_l <- ci[x_c,"lower"]
  Beta_raw_u <- ci[x_c,"upper"]
  Beta_m <- (10^(coef[x_c,"Value"])-1)*100
  Beta_l <- (10^(ci[x_c,"lower"])-1)*100
  Beta_u <- (10^(ci[x_c,"upper"])-1)*100
  P_value <- coef[x_c,"p-value"]
  SE_value <- coef[x_c,"Std.Error"]
  result <-
data.frame(Q=c("Q2"),Beta_m,Beta_l,Beta_u,Beta_raw_m,Beta_raw_l,Beta_raw_u,P_value,SE_value,
VIF_max,formula1)
  result$Beta <- paste(sprintf("%.2f",result$Beta_m),"(", sprintf("%.2f",result$Beta_l), ", ",
sprintf("%.2f",result$Beta_u), ")"), sep = "")
  result$P <- ifelse(result$P_value<0.0001,"<0.0001",sprintf("%.4f",result$P_value))
  result$SE <- sprintf("%.4f",result$SE_value)
  result <-
result[,c("Q","Beta","P","SE","Beta_m","Beta_l","Beta_u","Beta_raw_m","Beta_raw_l","Beta_raw_u",
"P_value","SE_value","VIF_max","formula1")]
}
return(result)
}

for (y1 in Order_Disease){
  for (y2 in unique(Outcome_Map_1$measure_name[Outcome_Map_1$cause_name==y1])) {
    for (x in c("NDVI","EVI","GS","TC")) { # y1="Non-communicable
diseases";y2="Deaths";x="NDVI"
      #merge data
      datax <- ExpoCov_1
      datay <- Outcome_Map_1[Outcome_Map_1$cause_name==y1 &
Outcome_Map_1$measure_name==y2, c("location_id','location_name','year','val','SpaLag_val")]
      data_all <- merge(datax,datay,all = T)

      if(x %in% c("GS","TC")){data_all <- na.omit(data_all)}
      for (c in
c(COV_list,"HealthExpend","HealthWorker","Vegetable","RedMeat","Alcohol","Smoke")) {data_all
<- fun_cov_cat(data_all,c)}

      data_all <- fun_cov_cat(data_all,"LandArea")
      data_all$LandArea_c <- as.integer(data_all$LandArea_c)

      if(y2=="YLDs"){x_1 <- paste0(x,"_c");data_all <- fun_nonline_2Q(data_all,x)}else{x_1 <- x}

```

```

#sen1:SCMMs model
data_all$XX <- data_all[,x]
data_all_1 <- data_all %>%
  group_by(location_id) %>%
  arrange(year) %>%
  mutate(x_lag1 = lag(XX, 1)) %>%
  ungroup()
data_all_1 <- as.data.frame(data_all_1)
result_sen1_x <- cbind(Outcome=y1,
measure=y2,Exposure=x,fun_model_weight_SCMMs(data=data_all_1,x=x_1,y="val",cov =
COV_list_c,var_w="LandArea_c"))
result_sen1 <- rbind(result_sen1,result_sen1_x)

#sen2: additionally controlling for health expenditure and health worker density
result_sen2_x <- cbind(Outcome=y1, measure=y2,Exposure=x,
  fun_model_weight(data=data_all,x=x_1,y="val",cov =
c(COV_list_c,"HealthExpend_c","HealthWorker_c"),var_w="LandArea_c"))
result_sen2 <- rbind(result_sen2,result_sen2_x)

#sen3: additionally controlling for vegetable and red meat consumption
result_sen3_x <- cbind(Outcome=y1, measure=y2,Exposure=x,
  fun_model_weight(data=data_all,x=x_1,y="val",cov =
c(COV_list_c,"Vegetable_c","RedMeat_c"),var_w="LandArea_c"))
result_sen3 <- rbind(result_sen3,result_sen3_x)

#sen4: additionally controlling for alcohol consumption and smoking prevalence
result_sen4_x <- cbind(Outcome=y1, measure=y2,Exposure=x,
  fun_model_weight(data=data_all,x=x_1,y="val",cov =
c(COV_list_c,"Alcohol_c","Smoke_c"),var_w="LandArea_c"))
result_sen4 <- rbind(result_sen4,result_sen4_x)

#sen5: restricted the analysis to countries with populations more than one million in 2010
list_c_pop <- unique(ExpoCov_1$location_id[ExpoCov_1$year == 2010 &
ExpoCov_1$Pop_num > 1000000])
data_all_2 <- subset(data_all,location_id %in% list_c_pop)
result_sen5_x <- cbind(Outcome=y1,
measure=y2,Exposure=x,fun_model_weight(data=data_all_2,x=x_1,y="val",cov =
COV_list_c,var_w="LandArea_c"))
result_sen5 <- rbind(result_sen5,result_sen5_x)

#sen6: excluded countries (territories) where the change in greenspace levels between 2000
and 2021 fell below the 2.5th %ile or exceeded the 97.5th %ile of greenspace levels
start_y <- ifelse(x %in% c("GS"),2001,2000)
end_y <- ifelse(x %in% c("TC"),2020,2021)

```

```

data_c <- merge(ExpoCov_1[ExpoCov_1$year==
start_y,c("location_id",x)],ExpoCov_1[ExpoCov_1$year==end_y,c("location_id",x)],by="location_id"
)
data_c$change <- data_c[,3]-data_c[,2]
list_c_green <- data_c$location_id[data_c$change > quantile(data_c$change,.025,na.rm=T) &
data_c$change < quantile(data_c$change,.975,na.rm=T)]
data_all_3 <- subset(data_all,location_id %in% list_c_green)
result_sen6_x <- cbind(Outcome=y1,
measure=y2,Exposure=x,fun_model_weight(data=data_all_3,x=x_1,y="val",cov =
COV_list_c,var_w="LandArea_c"))
result_sen6 <- rbind(result_sen6,result_sen6_x)

#sen7: excluding data in 2020 and 2021
data_all_5 <- data_all[data_all$year %in% 2000:2019,]
result_sen7_x <- cbind(Outcome=y1,
measure=y2,Exposure=x,fun_model_weight(data=data_all_5,x=x_1,y="val",cov =
COV_list_c,var_w="LandArea_c"))
result_sen7 <- rbind(result_sen7,result_sen7_x)

#sen8: used the population-weighted NDVI and EVI as exposure variables
data_all_4 <- data_all[,names(data_all)[!names(data_all) %in%
c("NDVI","EVI","GS","TC")]]
names(data_all_4)[names(data_all_4)==paste0(x,"_popw")] <- x
result_sen8_x <- cbind(Outcome=y1,
measure=y2,Exposure=x,fun_model_weight(data=data_all_4,x=x_1,y="val",cov =
COV_list_c,var_w="LandArea_c"))
result_sen8 <- rbind(result_sen8,result_sen8_x)

}}

list_analysis <- c("crude","main","sen1","sen2","sen3","sen4","sen5","sen6","sen7","sen8")

result_all <- data.frame()
for (i in list_analysis) {
result_x <- get(paste0("result_",i))
names(result_x)[names(result_x)=="Model"] <- "analysis"
result_x$analysis <- i
result_all <- rbind(result_all,result_x)
}

result_all$analysis <- sub("sen","SA",result_all$analysis)
result_all$analysis[result_all$analysis=="main"] <- "Main"
list_analysis_labels <- c("crude","Main","SA1","SA2","SA3","SA4","SA5","SA6","SA7","SA8")

```

```

result_all$analysis <- factor(result_all$analysis,ordered = T,levels = list_analysis_labels)
result_all$Exposure <- factor(result_all$Exposure,ordered = T,levels = c("NDVI","EVI","GS","TC"))
result_all$measure <- factor(result_all$measure,ordered = T,levels = Order_Measure)
result_all$Outcome <- factor(result_all$Outcome,ordered = T,levels = Order_Disease)
result_all <- result_all[order(result_all$analysis,result_all$Outcome,
result_all$measure,result_all$Exposure),]

```

```

result_all_1 <- result_all[,c("Outcome","measure","Exposure","Q","Beta","P","SE","analysis",
names(result_all)[! names(result_all) %in%
c("Outcome","measure","Exposure","Q","Beta","P","SE","analysis")])]
summary(result_all_1$VIF_max[result_all_1$analysis != "crude"])
names(result_all_1)[1:8] <- c("Disease","Index","Greenspace","Quintile","Estimate (95%
CI)","P","SE","Model")
write.csv(result_all_1,paste0(loc_save,"/Table S_Sensitivity Analyses.csv"),row.names = F)

```

```

result_all_p <- result_all
result_all_p$result <- NA
result_all_p$result[result_all_p$P_value<0.05 & result_all_p$Beta_m <0] <- " $\beta < 0$ ;  $p < 0.05$ "
result_all_p$result[result_all_p$P_value<0.05 & result_all_p$Beta_m >0] <- " $\beta > 0$ ;  $p < 0.05$ "
result_all_p$result[result_all_p$P_value>=0.05 & result_all_p$Beta_m <=0] <- " $\beta \leq 0$ ;  $p \geq 0.05$ "
result_all_p$result[result_all_p$P_value>=0.05 & result_all_p$Beta_m >=0] <- " $\beta \geq 0$ ;  $p \geq 0.05$ "

```

```

library(pheatmap)
library(RColorBrewer)
color_R = brewer.pal(n= 11, name = "PRGn")
cols <- c(" $\beta \leq 0$ ;  $p \geq 0.05$ " = color_R[7], " $\beta < 0$ ;  $p < 0.05$ " = color_R[9], " $\beta \geq 0$ ;  $p \geq 0.05$ " = color_R[5], " $\beta > 0$ ;
 $p < 0.05$ " = color_R[3])
mytheme_1 <- theme_bw()+
  theme(legend.title = element_blank(),
        panel.grid.major = element_line(colour = "white"),
        axis.title = element_blank(),
        text = element_text(size = 30, family = "serif", color = "black"),
        axis.text.x = element_text(size=28, color="black", family = "serif"),
        axis.text.y = element_text(size=32, color="black", family = "serif"),
        plot.margin = margin(t = 20, r = 20, b = 30, l = 20),
        strip.text = element_text(size = 32, color = "black", face = "bold"),
        panel.spacing = unit(1, "lines"),
        legend.position = "bottom",
        legend.text = element_text(size = 32, family = "serif", color = "black"),
        plot.title = element_text(color="black", size=28, family = "serif",
        face = "bold", hjust = -0.45))

```

```

cairo_pdf(paste0(loc_save,"/Figure S_Sensitivity Analyses.pdf"), width = 32, height = 28)
attach(result_all_p)

```

```

ggplot(data = result_all_p[result_all_p$analysis != "crude" & result_all_p$analysis != "Main" ],
  aes(x= analysis,
      y= Outcome,
      fill= result))+geom_tile(color = "white", lwd = 1.5)+
  scale_color_manual(values = cols, aesthetics = c("colour", "fill"))+
  scale_x_discrete(expand = c(0, 0), position = "top")+
  facet_grid(measure~Exposure, scales = "free",space = "free")+
  scale_y_discrete(limits = rev(Order_Disease))+
  mytheme_1
detach(result_all_p)
dev.off()

```

Part 2.6 Mediation analysis

```
library(bruceR)
```

```
var_medi <- c("PM2.5",'Temp')
```

```
Mediation_result <- data.frame()
```

```
for (y1 in "Non-communicable diseases"){
```

```
  for (y2 in c("Deaths","DALYs")) {
```

```
    for (x in c("NDVI","EVI","GS","TC")) {
```

```
      # merge data
```

```
      datax <- ExpoCov_1
```

```
      datay <- Outcome_Map_1[Outcome_Map_1$cause_name==y1 &
Outcome_Map_1$measure_name==y2, c("location_id","year","val","SpaLag_val")]
```

```
      data_all <- merge(datax,datay,all = T)
```

```
      if(x %in% c("GS","TC")){data_all <- na.omit(data_all)}
```

```
      for (c in c(COV_list)) {data_all <- fun_cov_cat(data_all,c)}
```

```
      data_all$val_log <- log10(data_all$val)
```

```
      Mediation <- PROCESS(data=data_all,y='val_log',x=x,meds=var_medi,clusters="location_id",
      covs=COV_list_c,ci='boot',nsim=1000,seed=0)
```

```
      for (i in 1:length(var_medi)) {
```

```
        Mediation1 <- Mediation$results[[i]]$mediation
```

```
        Indirect_m = Mediation1["Indirect (ab)","Effect"]
```

```
        Indirect_l = Mediation1["Indirect (ab)","LLCI"]
```

```
        Indirect_u = Mediation1["Indirect (ab)","ULCI"]
```

```
        P_Indirect = Mediation1["Indirect (ab)","p"]
```

```
        Direct_m = Mediation1["Direct (c)","Effect"]
```

```
        Direct_l = Mediation1["Direct (c)","LLCI"]
```

```
        Direct_u = Mediation1["Direct (c)","ULCI"]
```

```
        P_Direct = Mediation1["Direct (c)","p"]
```

```

total_m=Direct_m+Indirect_m
total_l=Direct_l+Indirect_l
total_u=Direct_m+Indirect_u
Indirect_p_m <- Indirect_m/total_m*100
Indirect_p_l <-
min(c(Indirect_l/total_l,Indirect_l/total_u,Indirect_u/total_l,Indirect_u/total_u))*100
Indirect_p_u <-
max(c(Indirect_l/total_l,Indirect_l/total_u,Indirect_u/total_l,Indirect_u/total_u))*100
Indirect_p <- paste(sprintf("%.2f",Indirect_p_m)," (", sprintf("%.2f",Indirect_p_l), ", ",
sprintf("%.2f",Indirect_p_u), ")"),sep = "")
Direct_p_m <- Direct_m/total_m*100
Direct_p_l <- min(c(Direct_l/total_l,Direct_l/total_u,Direct_u/total_l,Direct_u/total_u))*100
Direct_p_u <-
max(c(Direct_l/total_l,Direct_l/total_u,Direct_u/total_l,Direct_u/total_u))*100
Direct_p <- paste(sprintf("%.2f",Direct_p_m)," (", sprintf("%.2f",Direct_p_l), ", ",
sprintf("%.2f",Direct_p_u), ")"),sep = "")
Mediation1x <- data.frame(y=y2,x=x,m=var_medi[i],
                          Indirect_p,P_Indirect,
                          Direct_p,P_Direct,
                          Indirect_m,Indirect_l,Indirect_u,
                          Direct_m,Direct_l,Direct_u,
                          total_m,total_l,total_u)
Mediation_result <- rbind(Mediation_result,Mediation1x)
}}}}

```

```

Mediation_result$P_Indirect <-
ifelse(Mediation_result$P_Indirect<0.0001,"<0.0001",Mediation_result$P_Indirect)
Mediation_result$P_Direct <-
ifelse(Mediation_result$P_Direct<0.0001,"<0.0001",Mediation_result$P_Direct)

```

```

names(Mediation_result)[names(Mediation_result) %in%
c("y","x","m","Indirect_p","P_Indirect","Direct_p","P_Direct")] <-
c("Index","Greenspace","Mediator","Mediation effect","P_m","Direct effect","P_d")
Mediation_result$Mediator[Mediation_result$Mediator=="Temp"] <- "temperature"
Mediation_result$Mediator[Mediation_result$Mediator=="PM2.5"] <- "ambient air pollution"

```

```

write.csv(Mediation_result,paste0(loc_save,"/Table S_Mediation Analyses.csv"),row.names = F)

```

```

#####
## Part 3 Avoidable disease burden of NCDs

```

```
#####
```

```
# Part 3.1 counterfactual level of greenspace
```

```
ExpoCov_1 <- ExpoCov_1 %>%  
  group_by(location_id) %>%  
  mutate(NDVI_cf = max(NDVI)) %>%  
  ungroup()
```

```
# Part 3.2 age-sex specific  $\beta$ 
```

```
# Age-sex specific rate of NCDs
```

```
Burden_byAS <- read.csv("IHME-GBD_2021_DATA-ce24e337-1.csv")  
Burden_byAS$measure_name[Burden_byAS$measure_name=="DALYs (Disability-Adjusted Life  
Years)"] <- "DALYs"
```

```
# Spatially lagged variable
```

```
Burden_map_byAS <- data.frame()  
for (y in 2000:2021) {  
  for (a in unique(Burden_byAS$age_id)) {  
    for (s in unique(Burden_byAS$sex_id)) {  
      for (m in unique(Burden_byAS$measure_name)) {  
        Burden1 <- Burden_byAS[Burden_byAS$measure_name == m & Burden_byAS$year == y &  
          Burden_byAS$age_id == a & Burden_byAS$sex_id == s &  
          Burden_byAS$location_id %in% list_204c_location_id &  
          Burden_byAS$metric_name == "Rate",]  
  
        Burden1_map <- merge(Burden1, Map_1)  
        Burden1_map$SpaLag_val <- lag.listw(listw, Burden1_map$val)  
        Burden1_map <-  
        Burden1_map[,names(Burden1_map)[!names(Burden1_map)%in%"geometry"]]  
        Burden_map_byAS <- rbind(Burden_map_byAS, Burden1_map)  
        print(y)  
      }  
    }  
  }  
}  
Burden_map_byAS$age_name <- sub(" years", "", Burden_map_byAS$age_name)  
Burden_map_byAS$age_name <- sub(" year", "", Burden_map_byAS$age_name)  
table(Burden_map_byAS$age_name)  
order_age <- c("<1", "2-4", "5-9", "10-14", "15-19", "20-24", "25-29", "30-34", "35-39", "40-44", "45-49",  
  "50-54", "55-59", "60-64", "65-69", "70-74", "75-79", "80-84", "85+")
```

```
# Age-sex specific covariates: Education; Smoking
```

```
list_2Sex_id <- unique(Burden_map_byAS$sex_id)  
list_age_id <- unique(Burden_map_byAS$age_id)
```

```

POP <- read.csv("IHME-GBD_2021_DATA-33b90f55-1.CSV")
table(POP$age_name)
Education_AS <-
read.csv("IHME_GBD_2021_COV_1980_2021_EDUCATION_YRS_PC_Y2024M04D17.CSV")
Smoke_AS <-
read.csv("IHME_GBD_2021_COV_1980_2021_SMOKING_PREV_Y2024M04D17.CSV")
age_new <- list(age_new_1="<1",age_new_2="85+")
age_raw_e <- list(age_raw_e_1=c("Early Neonatal","Late Neonatal","1-5 months","6-11 months"),
                 age_raw_e_2=c("85 to 89","90 to 94","95 plus"))

# Education
names(Education_AS)[names(Education_AS)=="year_id"] <- "year"
names(Education_AS)[names(Education_AS)=="age_group_id"] <- "age_id"
Education_AS_1 <- Education_AS[!Education_AS$age_group_name %in%
c(age_raw_e[[1]],age_raw_e[[2])] &
                                Education_AS$age_id %in% list_age_id &
                                Education_AS$year %in% 2000:2021 &
                                Education_AS$location_id %in% list_204c_location_id,
                                c("location_id","year","age_id","sex_id","mean_value")]
names(Education_AS_1)[names(Education_AS_1)=="mean_value"] <- "Education"
for (a in 1:length(age_new)) { # a=1
  Education_AS_2 <- Education_AS[Education_AS$age_group_name %in% age_raw_e[[a]] &
                                Education_AS$year %in% 2000:2021 &
                                Education_AS$location_id %in% list_204c_location_id,]
  POP_age_raw <- POP[POP$location_id %in% list_204c_location_id &
                    POP$year %in% 2000:2021 & POP$sex_id %in% list_2Sex_id &
                    POP$age_id %in%
unique(Education_AS$age_id[Education_AS$age_group_name %in% age_raw_e[[a]]],)
  Data_age_raw <-
merge(Education_AS_2,POP_age_raw,by=c("location_id","year","age_id","sex_id"))
  Data_age_raw$multi <- Data_age_raw$mean_value*Data_age_raw$val
  agg_1 <-
aggregate(Data_age_raw$multi,by=list(location_id=Data_age_raw$location_id,year=Data_age_raw$year,sex_id=Data_age_raw$sex_id), FUN=sum)
  agg_2 <-
aggregate(Data_age_raw$val,by=list(location_id=Data_age_raw$location_id,year=Data_age_raw$year,sex_id=Data_age_raw$sex_id), FUN=sum)
  agg <- merge(agg_1,agg_2,by=c("location_id","year","sex_id"))
  agg$Education <- agg$x.x/agg$x.y
  agg$age_id <- unique(Burden_map_byAS$age_id[Burden_map_byAS$age_name==age_new[[a]])
  Education_AS_1 <- rbind(Education_AS_1,agg[,names(Education_AS_1)])
}

# Smoke

```

```

names(Smoke_AS)[names(Smoke_AS)=="year_id"] <- "year"
names(Smoke_AS)[names(Smoke_AS)=="age_group_id"] <- "age_id"
Smoke_AS_1 <- Smoke_AS[!Smoke_AS$age_group_name %in% c(age_raw_e[[1]],age_raw_e[[2])]
&
    Smoke_AS$age_id %in% list_age_id &
    Smoke_AS$year %in% 2000:2021 &
    Smoke_AS$location_id %in% list_204c_location_id,
    c("location_id","year","age_id","sex_id","mean_value")]
names(Smoke_AS_1)[names(Smoke_AS_1)=="mean_value"] <- "Smoke"
for (a in 1:length(age_new)) { # a=2
  Smoke_AS_2 <- Smoke_AS[Smoke_AS$age_group_name %in% age_raw_e[[a]] &
    Smoke_AS$year %in% 2000:2021 &
    Smoke_AS$location_id %in% list_204c_location_id,]
  POP_age_raw <- POP[POP$location_id %in% list_204c_location_id &
    POP$year %in% 2000:2021 & POP$sex_id %in% list_2Sex_id &
    POP$age_id %in%
unique(Smoke_AS$age_id[Smoke_AS$age_group_name %in% age_raw_e[[a]]],)
  Data_age_raw <- merge(Smoke_AS_2,POP_age_raw,by=c("location_id","year","age_id","sex_id"))
  Data_age_raw$multi <- Data_age_raw$mean_value*Data_age_raw$val
  agg_1 <-
aggregate(Data_age_raw$multi,by=list(location_id=Data_age_raw$location_id,year=Data_age_raw$year,sex_id=Data_age_raw$sex_id), FUN=sum)
  agg_2 <-
aggregate(Data_age_raw$val,by=list(location_id=Data_age_raw$location_id,year=Data_age_raw$year,sex_id=Data_age_raw$sex_id), FUN=sum)
  agg <- merge(agg_1,agg_2,by=c("location_id","year","sex_id"))
  agg$Smoke <- agg$x.x/agg$x.y
  agg$age_id <- unique(Burden_map_byAS$age_id[Burden_map_byAS$age_name==age_new[[a]])
  Smoke_AS_1 <- rbind(Smoke_AS_1,agg[,names(Smoke_AS_1)])
}

```

Age-sex-specific association

```

COV_list_AS <- c("Urbanicity","GDP","Education","Rain","SpaLag_val")
COV_list_AS_c <- paste0(COV_list_AS,"_c")
result_main_AS <- data.frame()
result_sen1_AS <- data.frame()
result_sen2_AS <- data.frame()
result_sen3_AS <- data.frame()
result_sen4_AS <- data.frame()
result_sen5_AS <- data.frame()
result_sen6_AS <- data.frame()
result_sen7_AS <- data.frame()
result_sen8_AS <- data.frame()

```

```

for (a in unique(Burden_map_byAS$age_id)) {
  for (s in unique(Burden_map_byAS$sex_id)) {
    for (x in c("NDVI")) {
      for (y in c("Deaths","DALYs")) { # a=6;s=1;x="NDVI";y="Deaths"
        #merge data
        datax1 <-
ExpoCov_1[,c("location_id","year",x,paste0(x,"_popw"),COV_list[!COV_list%in%c("FemaleP","Education","SpaLag_val")], "LandArea", "HealthExpend", "HealthWorker", "Vegetable", "RedMeat", "Alcohol")]
        datax2 <- Education_AS_1[Education_AS_1$age_id==a &
Education_AS_1$sex_id==s,c("location_id","year","Education")]
        datax <- merge(datax1,datax2)
        datax3 <- Smoke_AS_1[Smoke_AS_1$age_id==a &
Smoke_AS_1$sex_id==s,c("location_id","year","Smoke")]
        datax <- merge(datax,datax3)

        datay <- Burden_map_byAS[Burden_map_byAS$measure_name==y &
Burden_map_byAS$age_id==a & Burden_map_byAS$sex_id==s,
          c("location_id","location_name","year","val","SpaLag_val")]
        data_all <- merge(datax,datay)

        for (c in
c(COV_list_AS,"HealthExpend","HealthWorker","Vegetable","RedMeat","Alcohol","Smoke"))
{data_all <- fun_cov_cat(data_all,c)}
        data_all <- fun_cov_cat(data_all,"LandArea")
        data_all$LandArea_c <- as.integer(data_all$LandArea_c)

        #main
        result_main1 <- cbind(Exposure=x, Outcome=unique(Burden_map_byAS$cause_name),
measure=y,
          age_id=a,
age_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$age_name[Burden_map_byAS$age_id==a]),
          sex_id=s,
sex_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$sex_name[Burden_map_byAS$sex_id==s]),
          fun_model_weight(data=data_all,x=x,y="val",cov =
COV_list_AS_c,var_w="LandArea_c"))
        result_main_AS <- rbind(result_main_AS,result_main1)

        #sen1:SCMMs model
        data_all$XX <- data_all[,x]
        data_all_1 <- data_all %>%
          group_by(location_id) %>%
          arrange(year) %>%
          mutate(x_lag1 = lag(XX, 1)) %>%

```

```

    ungroup()
    data_all_1 <- as.data.frame(data_all_1)
    result_sen1_AS_x <- cbind(Exposure=x,
Outcome=unique(Burden_map_byAS$cause_name), measure=y,
                        age_id=a,
age_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$age_name[Burden_map_byAS$age_id==a]),
                        sex_id=s,
sex_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$sex_name[Burden_map_byAS$sex_id==s]),

fun_model_weight_SCMMs(data=data_all_1,x=x,y="val",cov =
COV_list_AS_c,var_w="LandArea_c"))
    result_sen1_AS <- rbind(result_sen1_AS,result_sen1_AS_x)

    #sen2: additionally controlling for health expenditure and health worker density
    result_sen2_AS_x <- cbind(Exposure=x,
Outcome=unique(Burden_map_byAS$cause_name), measure=y,
                        age_id=a,
age_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$age_name[Burden_map_byAS$age_id==a]),
                        sex_id=s,
sex_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$sex_name[Burden_map_byAS$sex_id==s]),
                        fun_model_weight(data=data_all,x=x,y="val",cov =
c(COV_list_AS_c,"HealthExpend_c","HealthWorker_c"),var_w="LandArea_c"))
    result_sen2_AS <- rbind(result_sen2_AS,result_sen2_AS_x)

    #sen3: additionally controlling for vegetable and red meat consumption
    result_sen3_AS_x <- cbind(Exposure=x,
Outcome=unique(Burden_map_byAS$cause_name), measure=y,
                        age_id=a,
age_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$age_name[Burden_map_byAS$age_id==a]),
                        sex_id=s,
sex_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$sex_name[Burden_map_byAS$sex_id==s]),
                        fun_model_weight(data=data_all,x=x,y="val",cov =
c(COV_list_AS_c,"Vegetable_c","RedMeat_c"),var_w="LandArea_c"))
    result_sen3_AS <- rbind(result_sen3_AS,result_sen3_AS_x)

    #sen4: additionally controlling for alcohol consumption and smoking prevalence
    if(max(datax$Smoke)!=0){
        result_sen4_AS_x <- cbind(Exposure=x,
Outcome=unique(Burden_map_byAS$cause_name), measure=y,
                        age_id=a,
age_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$age_name[Burden_map_byAS$age_id==a]),
                        sex_id=s,
sex_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$sex_name[Burden_map_byAS$sex_id==s]),
                        fun_model_weight(data=data_all,x=x,y="val",cov =

```

```

c(COV_list_AS_c,"Alcohol_c","Smoke_c"),var_w="LandArea_c"))
  }else{
    result_sen4_AS_x <- cbind(Exposure=x,
Outcome=unique(Burden_map_byAS$cause_name), measure=y,
    age_id=a,
age_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$age_name[Burden_map_byAS$age_id==a]),
    sex_id=s,
sex_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$sex_name[Burden_map_byAS$sex_id==s]),
    fun_model_weight(data=data_all,x=x,y="val",cov =
c(COV_list_AS_c,"Alcohol_c"),var_w="LandArea_c"))
  }
  result_sen4_AS <- rbind(result_sen4_AS,result_sen4_AS_x)

#sen5: restricted the analysis to countries with populations more than one million in 2010
list_c_pop <- unique(ExpoCov_1$location_id[ExpoCov_1$year == 2010 &
ExpoCov_1$Pop_num > 1000000])
data_all_2 <- subset(data_all,location_id %in% list_c_pop)
result_sen5_AS_x <- cbind(Exposure=x,
Outcome=unique(Burden_map_byAS$cause_name), measure=y,
    age_id=a,
age_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$age_name[Burden_map_byAS$age_id==a]),
    sex_id=s,
sex_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$sex_name[Burden_map_byAS$sex_id==s]),
    fun_model_weight(data=data_all_2,x=x,y="val",cov =
COV_list_AS_c,var_w="LandArea_c"))
  result_sen5_AS <- rbind(result_sen5_AS,result_sen5_AS_x)

#sen6: excluded countries (territories) where the change in greenspace levels between 2000
and 2021 fell below the 2.5th %ile or exceeded the 97.5th %ile of greenspace levels
data_c <- merge(ExpoCov_1[ExpoCov_1$year==
2000,c("location_id",x)],ExpoCov_1[ExpoCov_1$year==2021,c("location_id",x)],by="location_id")
data_c$change <- data_c[,3]-data_c[,2]
list_c_green <- data_c$location_id[data_c$change > quantile(data_c$change,.025,na.rm=T)
& data_c$change < quantile(data_c$change,.975,na.rm=T)]
data_all_3 <- subset(data_all,location_id %in% list_c_green)
result_sen6_AS_x <- cbind(Exposure=x,
Outcome=unique(Burden_map_byAS$cause_name), measure=y,
    age_id=a,
age_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$age_name[Burden_map_byAS$age_id==a]),
    sex_id=s,
sex_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$sex_name[Burden_map_byAS$sex_id==s]),
    fun_model_weight(data=data_all_3,x=x,y="val",cov =
COV_list_AS_c,var_w="LandArea_c"))
  result_sen6_AS <- rbind(result_sen6_AS,result_sen6_AS_x)

```

```

#sen7: excluding data in 2020 and 2021
data_all_5 <- data_all[data_all$year %in% 2000:2019,]
result_sen7_AS_x <- cbind(Exposure=x,
Outcome=unique(Burden_map_byAS$cause_name), measure=y,
age_id=a,
age_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$age_name[Burden_map_byAS$age_id==a]),
sex_id=s,
sex_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$sex_name[Burden_map_byAS$sex_id==s]),
fun_model_weight(data=data_all_5,x=x,y="val",cov =
COV_list_AS_c,var_w="LandArea_c"))
result_sen7_AS <- rbind(result_sen7_AS,result_sen7_AS_x)

```

```

#sen8: used the population-weighted NDVI and EVI as exposure variables
data_all_4 <- data_all[,names(data_all)[!names(data_all) %in% c(x)]]
names(data_all_4)[names(data_all_4)==paste0(x,"_popw")] <- x
result_sen8_AS_x <- cbind(Exposure=x,
Outcome=unique(Burden_map_byAS$cause_name), measure=y,
age_id=a,
age_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$age_name[Burden_map_byAS$age_id==a]),
sex_id=s,
sex_name=unique(Burden_map_byAS$sex_name[Burden_map_byAS$sex_id==s]),
fun_model_weight(data=data_all_4,x=x,y="val",cov =
COV_list_AS_c,var_w="LandArea_c"))
result_sen8_AS <- rbind(result_sen8_AS,result_sen8_AS_x)

```

```

}}}}

```

```

list_analysis <- c("main","sen1","sen2","sen3","sen4","sen5","sen6","sen7","sen8")
result_all_AS <- data.frame()
for (i in list_analysis) {
result_x <- get(paste0("result_",i,"_AS"))
names(result_x)[names(result_x)=="Model"] <- "analysis"
result_x$analysis <- i
result_all_AS <- rbind(result_all_AS,result_x)
}
summary(result_all_AS$VIF_max)

```

```

result_all_AS$analysis <- factor(result_all_AS$analysis,ordered = T,levels = list_analysis)
result_all_AS$measure <- factor(result_all_AS$measure,ordered = T,levels = c("Deaths","DALYs"))
result_all_AS <- result_all_AS[order(result_all_AS$analysis,result_all_AS$measure),]

```

```

result_main_AS$label_P <- ifelse(result_main_AS$P_value<0.05,"*"," ")
result_main_AS$measure <- factor(result_main_AS$measure,ordered = T,levels =

```

```
c("Deaths","DALYs"))
```

```
p <- ggplot(result_main_AS,aes(x=age_name,y=Beta_m))+  
  geom_errorbar(aes(ymin=Beta_l,ymax=Beta_u),width=0.5,size=1,alpha=0.5)+  
  geom_point(size=1.5)+  
  geom_hline(yintercept=0,linetype="dashed")+  
  geom_text(aes(label=label_P,x=age_name,y=Beta_l),  
            vjust='center',size=8,show.legend=F,nudge_y=-0.4,alpha=1)+  
  scale_x_discrete(limits=c(order_age))+  
  labs(y="% Percentage change in the rates of outcomes",x=NULL)+  
  facet_grid(measure~sex_name)+  
  theme_bw()+  
  theme(text=element_text(size=10,color="black",family="serif"),  
        axis.text.x=element_text(size=10,color="black",family="serif",  
                                   angle=45,vjust=0.2,hjust=0),  
        axis.text.y=element_text(size=10,color="black",family="serif"),  
        axis.title.x=element_text(vjust=-1,face="bold"),  
        panel.spacing=unit(1,"lines"),  
        plot.margin=margin(t=20,r=20,b=20,l=20),  
        strip.text=element_text(size=10,color="black",face="bold"),  
        panel.grid.major=element_line(colour="grey95",size=0.1),  
        panel.grid.minor=element_line(colour="grey95",size=0.1))
```

```
ggsave(file=paste0(loc_save,"/Figure S_Age and sex specific associations.pdf"),plot=p,width=  
11.69,height=8.27)
```

```
# Part 3.3 Age-sex-specific population
```

```
POP_AS_1 <- POP[POP$age_id %in% list_age_id & POP$sex_id %in%  
list_2Sex_id,c("location_id","year","age_id","sex_id","val","upper","lower")]  
POP_AS_2 <- POP[POP$age_name %in% c("85-89 years","90-94 years","95+ years") &  
POP$sex_id %in% list_2Sex_id,]  
POP_AS_2_agg_m <-  
aggregate(POP_AS_2$val,by=list(location_id=POP_AS_2$location_id,year=POP_AS_2$year,sex_id  
=POP_AS_2$sex_id),FUN=sum)  
POP_AS_2_agg_l <-  
aggregate(POP_AS_2$lower,by=list(location_id=POP_AS_2$location_id,year=POP_AS_2$year,sex_  
id=POP_AS_2$sex_id),FUN=sum)  
POP_AS_2_agg_u <-  
aggregate(POP_AS_2$upper,by=list(location_id=POP_AS_2$location_id,year=POP_AS_2$year,sex_  
id=POP_AS_2$sex_id),FUN=sum)  
names(POP_AS_2_agg_m)[names(POP_AS_2_agg_m)=="x"] <- "val"  
names(POP_AS_2_agg_l)[names(POP_AS_2_agg_l)=="x"] <- "lower"
```

```

names(POP_AS_2_agg_u)[names(POP_AS_2_agg_u)=="x"] <- "upper"
POP_AS_2_agg <- merge(POP_AS_2_agg_m,POP_AS_2_agg_l)
POP_AS_2_agg <- merge(POP_AS_2_agg,POP_AS_2_agg_u)
POP_AS_2_agg$age_id <-
unique(Burden_map_byAS$age_id[Burden_map_byAS$age_name=="85+"])
POP_AS <- rbind(POP_AS_1,POP_AS_2_agg)

```

```
# Part 3.4 Location hierarchy
```

```
# Hierarchies:
```

```
# 1. global
```

```
# 2. four World Bank income levels
```

```
# 3. twenty-one GBD regions
```

```
# Source:
```

```
# 1. Global Burden of Disease Collaborative Network. Global Burden of Disease Study 2021 (GBD 2021) Cause, REI, and Location Hierarchies. Seattle, United States of America: Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME), 2024.
```

```
# 2. World Bank:
```

```
https://datahelpdesk.worldbank.org/knowledgebase/articles/906519-world-bank-country-and-lending-groups
```

```
HIERARCHY <- read.csv("LOCATION_HIERARCHY.csv")
```

```
# Part 3.5 Life expectancy
```

```
data <- read.csv("IHME-GBD_2021_DATA-a2639a82-1.csv") #age-sex-specific all-cause mortality
```

```
data$age_name <- sub(" years","",data$age_name)
```

```
data$age_name <- sub(" year","",data$age_name)
```

```
data <- data[which(data$age_name %in% order_age & data$sex_name %in% c("Female","Male")),]
```

```
data$mortality <- data$val/100000
```

```
Life_table <- data.frame()
```

```
for (y in 2000:2021) {
```

```
  for (l in list_204c_location_id) {
```

```
    for (s in list_2Sex_id) {# y=2000;l=75;s= 1
```

```
      data_1 <- data[which(data$year == y & data$location_id == l & data$sex_id == s),
```

```
c("location_id","location_name","year","sex_id","sex_name","age_id","age_name","mortality")]
```

```
  data_1$age_name <- factor(data_1$age_name,ordered = T,levels = order_age)
```

```
  data_1 <- data_1[order(data_1$age_name),]
```

```
  #n
```

```
  data_1$n <- ifelse(data_1$age_name %in% c("<1","2-4","85+"),NA,5)
```

```

data_1$n[data_1$age_name == "<1"] <- 1
data_1$n[data_1$age_name == "2-4"] <- 4

#a
data_1$a<- ifelse(data_1$age_name %in% c("<1","2-4","85+"),NA,2.5)
for (x in 1:nrow(data_1)) { # x=1
  a <- data_1[x, "age_name"]
  m_0to1 <- as.numeric(data_1$mortality[data_1$age_name == "<1"])
  if (a == "<1" & m_0to1 >= 0.107 & s == 1){
    data_1[x, "a"] <- 0.330
  }else if (a == "<1" & m_0to1 >= 0.107 & s == 2){
    data_1[x, "a"] <- 0.350
  }else if (a == "<1" & m_0to1 < 0.107 & s == 1){
    data_1[x, "a"] <- 0.045+2.684*m_0to1
  }else if (a == "<1" & m_0to1 < 0.107 & s == 2){
    data_1[x, "a"] <- 0.053+2.800*m_0to1
  }else if (a == "2-4" & m_0to1 >= 0.107 & s == 1){
    data_1[x, "a"] <- 1.352
  }else if (a == "2-4" & m_0to1 >= 0.107 & s == 2){
    data_1[x, "a"] <- 1.361
  }else if (a == "2-4" & m_0to1 < 0.107 & s == 1){
    data_1[x, "a"] <- 1.651-2.816*m_0to1
  }else if (a == "2-4" & m_0to1 < 0.107 & s == 2){
    data_1[x, "a"] <- 1.522-1.518*m_0to1
  }else{
    data_1[x, "a"] <- data_1[x, "a"]
  }
}
summary(data_1$a)

#q
data_1$q <- ifelse(data_1$age_name %in% c("85+"),1,

(data_1$n*as.numeric(data_1$mortality))/(1+((data_1$n-data_1$a)*as.numeric(data_1$mortality))))
data_1$q <- ifelse(data_1$age_name %in% c("<1"),as.numeric(data_1$mortality),data_1$q)

summary(data_1$q)
data_1$q <- as.numeric(data_1$q)

#l, d
data_1$l <- NA
data_1$d <- NA
for (age in 2:(length(order_age))) { # age = 2
  #l=100000 (0 year)
  data_1$l[data_1$age_name == order_age[1]] <- 100000

```

```

data_1$d[data_1$age_name == order_age[1]] <- 100000*data_1$q[data_1$age_name ==
order_age[1]]

data_xx <- data_1[which(data_1$age_name == order_age[age]),]
data_xx_1 <- data_1[which(data_1$age_name == order_age[age-1]),]
data_1$l[data_1$age_name == order_age[age]] <- data_xx_1$l-data_xx_1$d
data_1$d[data_1$age_name == order_age[age]] <- (data_xx_1$l-data_xx_1$d)*data_xx$q
}
summary(data_1$d)

#L
order <- 1:length(order_age)
data_order_age <- data.frame(order_age,order)

data_1$L <- NA
for (i in 1:nrow(data_1)) { # i=1
  if(data_1[i,"age_name"] != "85+"){
    order_i <- data_order_age$order[data_order_age$order_age == data_1[i,"age_name"]]
    d_x <- data_1[i,"d"]
    a_x <- data_1[i,"a"]
    n_x <- data_1[i,"n"]
    l_xn <- data_1$l[data_1$age_name == data_order_age$order_age[data_order_age$order
== order_i+1]]
    data_1[i,"L"] <- d_x*a_x+l_xn*n_x
  }else{
    data_1[i,"L"] <- data_1[i,"d"]/(as.numeric(data_1[i,"mortality"]))
  }
}
summary(data_1$L)

#T
data_1$Tx <- NA
for (age in (length(order_age)-1):1) {
  #L
  data_1$Tx[data_1$age_name == order_age[length(order_age)]] <-
data_1$L[data_1$age_name == order_age[length(order_age)]]
  data_xx_1 <- data_1[which(data_1$age_name %in% order_age[length(order_age):age]),]
  data_1$Tx[data_1$age_name == order_age[age]] <- sum(data_xx_1$L)
}
summary(data_1$Tx)

#e
data_1$e <- data_1$Tx/data_1$l

Life_table <- rbind(Life_table,data_1)

```

```

print(paste0(y,"--",l,"--",s))

}}

# Part 3.4 Uncertainty analysis
n=500
fun_avoid_disease_burden_main <- function(sap,analysis_code){
  #sap=4; analysis_code="main"

  #baseline burden
  set.seed(sap)
  Burden_byAS$base_burden_un <- rnorm(nrow(Burden_byAS),Burden_byAS$val,
                                     (Burden_byAS$upper-Burden_byAS$lower)/(2*1.96))

  seed_counter <- sap+500
  while(any(Burden_byAS["base_burden_un"] <= 0)) {
    set.seed(seed_counter)
    negative_indices <- which(Burden_byAS["base_burden_un"] <= 0)
    Burden_byAS[negative_indices,"base_burden_un"] <- rnorm(length(negative_indices),

Burden_byAS[negative_indices,"val"],

(Burden_byAS[negative_indices,"upper"]-Burden_byAS[negative_indices,"lower"])/(2*1.96))
    seed_counter <- seed_counter + 500
  }

  #greenspace level difference
  set.seed(sap)
  ExpoCov_1 <- as.data.frame(ExpoCov_1)
  ExpoCov_1$green_un <- runif(nrow(ExpoCov_1),ExpoCov_1$NDVI-0.0148,ExpoCov_1$NDVI)
  ExpoCov_1$green_un <- ifelse(ExpoCov_1$green_un<0,0,ExpoCov_1$green_un)

  ExpoCov_1$green_diff_un <- ExpoCov_1$NDVI_cf-ExpoCov_1$green_un
  Data_for_DB <-
merge(Burden_byAS[,c("location_id","location_name","year","measure_name","age_id","age_name",
"sex_id","sex_name","val","base_burden_un")],
      ExpoCov_1[,c("location_id","year","NDVI",
"NDVI_cf","green_un","green_diff_un")],
      by=c("location_id","year"))
  names(Data_for_DB)[names(Data_for_DB)=="measure_name"] <- "measure"
  names(Data_for_DB)[names(Data_for_DB)=="val"] <- "base_burden"

```

```

#estimate
result_all_AS_x <- result_all_AS[result_all_AS$analysis == analysis_code,]
set.seed(sap)
result_all_AS_x$Beta_raw_un <-
rnorm(nrow(result_all_AS_x),result_all_AS_x$Beta_raw_m,(result_all_AS_x$Beta_raw_u-result_all
_AS_x$Beta_raw_l)/(2*1.96))

seed_counter <- sap+500
while(any(result_all_AS_x[,"Beta_raw_un"] >= 0)) {
  set.seed(seed_counter)
  negative_indices <- which(result_all_AS_x[,"Beta_raw_un"] >= 0)
  result_all_AS_x[negative_indices,"Beta_raw_un"] <- rnorm(length(negative_indices),

result_all_AS_x[negative_indices,"Beta_raw_m"],

(result_all_AS_x[negative_indices,"Beta_raw_u"]-result_all_AS_x[negative_indices,"Beta_raw_l"])/(
2*1.96))
  seed_counter <- seed_counter + 500
}
result_all_AS_x$Beta_raw_un <-
ifelse(result_all_AS_x$P_value>=0.05,0,result_all_AS_x$Beta_raw_un)

Data_for_DB <-
merge(Data_for_DB,result_all_AS_x[,c("measure","age_id","sex_id","analysis","Beta","P","Beta_raw
_m","Beta_raw_l","Beta_raw_u","P_value","Beta_raw_un")],
      by=c("measure","age_id","sex_id"))

#population
set.seed(sap)
POP_AS$pop_un <-
rnorm(nrow(POP_AS),POP_AS$val,(POP_AS$upper-POP_AS$lower)/(2*1.96))
seed_counter <- sap+500
while(any(POP_AS[,"pop_un"] <= 0)) {
  set.seed(seed_counter)
  negative_indices <- which(POP_AS[,"pop_un"] <= 0)
  POP_AS[negative_indices,"pop_un"] <- rnorm(length(negative_indices),
                                           POP_AS[negative_indices,"val"],

(POP_AS[negative_indices,"upper"]-POP_AS[negative_indices,"lower"])/(2*1.96))
  seed_counter <- seed_counter + 500
}

Data_for_DB <-
merge(Data_for_DB,POP_AS[,c("location_id","year","age_id","sex_id","val","pop_un")],

```

```

        by=c("location_id","year","age_id","sex_id"))
names(Data_for_DB)[names(Data_for_DB)=="val"] <- "pop"

#avoidable disease burden
Data_for_DB$avoid_DB_num_un <-
(-1)*(10^(Data_for_DB$green_diff_un*Data_for_DB$Beta_raw_un)-1)*Data_for_DB$base_burden_
un/100000*Data_for_DB$pop_un
Data_for_DB$sap <- sap

if(min(Data_for_DB$avoid_DB_num_un) <0){print(paste0("Error: ",sap))}

print(sap)
return(Data_for_DB)
}

result_list <- vector("list",n)
for (s in 1:n) {
  result_list[[s]] <- fun_avoid_disease_burden_main(sap=s,analysis_code="main")
}
result_avoid_DB <- do.call(rbind, result_list)

# Aggregate the results:
# 1. country/territory level:
# (1) sum (by location_id, measure, analysis, simulations)
# (2) mean+95%UI (by location_id,analysis,measure)
result_avoid_DB_204c <- aggregate(cbind(avoid_DB_num_un, base_burden_un) ~ location_id +
measure + analysis + sap,
                                data = result_avoid_DB, FUN = sum)
result_avoid_DB_204c$avoid_DB_pro_un <-
result_avoid_DB_204c$avoid_DB_num_un/result_avoid_DB_204c$base_burden_un*100
result_avoid_DB_204c_1 <- result_avoid_DB_204c %>%
  group_by(location_id,measure,analysis) %>%
  summarise(
    avoid_DB_num_un_m = mean(avoid_DB_num_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_num_un_l = quantile(avoid_DB_num_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_num_un_u = quantile(avoid_DB_num_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_pro_un_m = mean(avoid_DB_pro_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_pro_un_l = quantile(avoid_DB_pro_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_pro_un_u = quantile(avoid_DB_pro_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE)
  )

## Categorized the 204 countries (territories) into different groups
result_avoid_DB_204c_2 <- merge(HIERARCHY,result_avoid_DB_204c,by="location_id")

```

```

result_avoid_DB_204c_3 <-
merge(HIERARCHY[,c("location_id","location_name")],result_avoid_DB_204c_1,by="location_id")

# global
result_avoid_DB_all_1 <- aggregate(cbind(avoid_DB_num_un, base_burden_un) ~
location_id_l1+location_name_l1+measure + analysis + sap,
                                data = result_avoid_DB_204c_2, FUN = sum)
result_avoid_DB_all_1$avoid_DB_pro_un <-
result_avoid_DB_all_1$avoid_DB_num_un/result_avoid_DB_all_1$base_burden_un*100
result_avoid_DB_all_1 <- result_avoid_DB_all_1 %>%
  group_by(location_id_l1,location_name_l1, analysis, measure) %>%
  summarise(
    avoid_DB_num_un_m = mean(avoid_DB_num_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_num_un_l = quantile(avoid_DB_num_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_num_un_u = quantile(avoid_DB_num_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_pro_un_m = mean(avoid_DB_pro_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_pro_un_l = quantile(avoid_DB_pro_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_pro_un_u = quantile(avoid_DB_pro_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE)
  )
names(result_avoid_DB_all_1)[names(result_avoid_DB_all_1) %in%
c("location_id_l1","location_name_l1")] <- c("location_id","location_name")
result_avoid_DB_all_1$location_level <- 1
write.csv(result_avoid_DB_all_1,paste0(loc_save,"/result_avoid_DB_all_1_",unique(result_avoid_D
B$analysis),"_",n,".csv"),row.names = F)

# four World Bank income levels
result_avoid_DB_all_2 <- aggregate(cbind(avoid_DB_num_un, base_burden_un) ~
location_id_l2+location_name_l2+measure + sap,
                                data = result_avoid_DB_204c_2, FUN = sum)
result_avoid_DB_all_2$avoid_DB_pro_un <-
result_avoid_DB_all_2$avoid_DB_num_un/result_avoid_DB_all_2$base_burden_un*100
result_avoid_DB_all_2 <- result_avoid_DB_all_2 %>%
  group_by(location_id_l2,location_name_l2, measure) %>%
  summarise(
    avoid_DB_num_un_m = mean(avoid_DB_num_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_num_un_l = quantile(avoid_DB_num_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_num_un_u = quantile(avoid_DB_num_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_pro_un_m = mean(avoid_DB_pro_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_pro_un_l = quantile(avoid_DB_pro_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_pro_un_u = quantile(avoid_DB_pro_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE)
  )
names(result_avoid_DB_all_2)[names(result_avoid_DB_all_2) %in%
c("location_id_l2","location_name_l2")] <- c("location_id","location_name")
result_avoid_DB_all_2$location_level <- 2

```

```

result_avoid_DB_all_2 <- result_avoid_DB_all_2[result_avoid_DB_all_2$location_id!=5,]

# twenty-one GBD regions
result_avoid_DB_all_3 <- aggregate(cbind(avoid_DB_num_un, base_burden_un) ~
location_id_l3+location_name_l3+measure + sap,
                                data = result_avoid_DB_204c_2, FUN = sum)
result_avoid_DB_all_3$avoid_DB_pro_un <-
result_avoid_DB_all_3$avoid_DB_num_un/result_avoid_DB_all_3$base_burden_un*100
result_avoid_DB_all_3 <- result_avoid_DB_all_3 %>%
  group_by(location_id_l3,location_name_l3, measure) %>%
  summarise(
    avoid_DB_num_un_m = mean(avoid_DB_num_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_num_un_l = quantile(avoid_DB_num_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_num_un_u = quantile(avoid_DB_num_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_pro_un_m = mean(avoid_DB_pro_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_pro_un_l = quantile(avoid_DB_pro_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_pro_un_u = quantile(avoid_DB_pro_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE)
  )
names(result_avoid_DB_all_3)[names(result_avoid_DB_all_3) %in%
c("location_id_l3","location_name_l3")] <- c("location_id","location_name")
result_avoid_DB_all_3$location_level <- 3

result_avoid_DB_all_4 <- result_avoid_DB_204c_3[result_avoid_DB_204c_3$analysis=="main",

names(result_avoid_DB_204c_3)[names(result_avoid_DB_204c_3) %in%
names(result_avoid_DB_all_1)]]
result_avoid_DB_all_4$location_level <- 4

result_avoid_DB_all <- rbind(result_avoid_DB_all_1, result_avoid_DB_all_2, result_avoid_DB_all_3,
result_avoid_DB_all_4)
result_avoid_DB_all$measure <- factor(result_avoid_DB_all$measure,ordered = T,levels =
c("Deaths","DALYs"))
result_avoid_DB_all <-
result_avoid_DB_all[order(result_avoid_DB_all$location_level,result_avoid_DB_all$location_id,result_avoid_DB_all$measure),]

result_avoid_DB_all$avoid_DB_num_Million <-
paste0(sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_DB_all$avoid_DB_num_un_m/1000000),"
(",sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_DB_all$avoid_DB_num_un_l/1000000),"
",sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_DB_all$avoid_DB_num_un_u/1000000),")")
result_avoid_DB_all$avoid_DB_num <-
paste0(sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_DB_all$avoid_DB_num_un_m),
(",sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_DB_all$avoid_DB_num_un_l),"
",sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_DB_all$avoid_DB_num_un_u),")")

```

```

result_avoid_DB_all$avoid_DB_pro <-
paste0(sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_DB_all$avoid_DB_pro_un_m),"
(",sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_DB_all$avoid_DB_pro_un_l),"
",sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_DB_all$avoid_DB_pro_un_u),"")
result_avoid_DB_all_t <-
result_avoid_DB_all[,c("location_name","measure","avoid_DB_num","avoid_DB_pro","avoid_DB_n
um_Million","avoid_DB_num_un_m","avoid_DB_pro_un_m")]
names(result_avoid_DB_all_t) <- c("Location","Index","Number of preventable deaths","Percentage
of preventable deaths (%)","Number of preventable deaths
(million)","preventable_DB_num_un_m","preventable_DB_pro_un_m")

write.csv(result_avoid_DB_all_t,paste0(loc_save, "/Table S_Preventable disease
burden_main", "_",n,".csv"),row.names = F)

```

```

#####
## Part 4 Avoidable economic burden of NCDs
#####

```

```

# Part 4.1 t: the average number of life-years lost
# age- and sex-specific avoidable NCDs-related deaths
data_N <- result_avoid_DB[result_avoid_DB$measure == "Deaths",]
data_N_1 <- data_N %>%
  group_by(analysis,location_id,year,age_id,sex_id) %>%
  summarise(
    avoid_DB_num_un_m = mean(avoid_DB_num_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_num_un_l = quantile(avoid_DB_num_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_num_un_u = quantile(avoid_DB_num_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE)
  )

t_data <- merge(data_N_1,Life_table,by=c("location_id","year","age_id","sex_id"))
t_data$avoid_DB_num_un_m_xLE <- t_data$avoid_DB_num_un_m*t_data$e
t_data_1 <- t_data %>%
  group_by(analysis,location_id, year) %>%
  dplyr::summarize(
    NxLE_m = sum(avoid_DB_num_un_m_xLE),
    N_m = sum(avoid_DB_num_un_m)
  )
t_data_1$t <- as.integer(ceiling(t_data_1$NxLE_m/t_data_1$N_m))
summary(t_data_1$t)
summary(t_data_1$N_m[is.na(t_data_1$t)])

```

```
# Part 4.2 N: number of avoidable NCDs-related deaths
```

```
data_N_2<- data_N %>%  
  group_by(analysis,location_id,year) %>%  
  summarise(  
    avoid_DB_num_un_m = mean(avoid_DB_num_un, na.rm = TRUE),  
    avoid_DB_num_un_l = quantile(avoid_DB_num_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),  
    avoid_DB_num_un_u = quantile(avoid_DB_num_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE)  
  )
```

```
data_for_EB <- merge(data_N_2,t_data_1[,c("analysis","location_id","year","t")],  
  by= c("analysis","location_id","year"),all=T)
```

```
# Part 4.3 GDP (Gross Domestic Product)
```

```
# 1. GDP per person (2021 Purchasing Power Parity-Adjusted Dollars)
```

```
# Source: Global Burden of Disease Collaborative Network. Gross Domestic Product Per Capita  
1960-2050 - FGH 2021. Seattle, United States of America: Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation  
(IHME), 2023.
```

```
GDP <- read.csv("IHME_GDP_1960_2050_Y2023M01D13.CSV")  
GDP <- GDP[GDP$location_id %in% list_204c_location_id & GDP$year %in%  
2000:2021,c("location_id","year","gdp_ppp_mean","gdp_ppp_lower","gdp_ppp_upper")]  
data_for_EB <- merge(data_for_EB,GDP,by= c("location_id","year"),all=T)
```

```
# 2.  $\alpha$ : the growth rate of per capita GDP
```

```
GDP_1 <- GDP[which(GDP$year == 2000),c("location_id","gdp_ppp_mean")]  
GDP_2 <- GDP[which(GDP$year == 2021),c("location_id","gdp_ppp_mean")]  
GDP_3 <- merge(GDP_1,GDP_2,by=c("location_id"))  
GDP_3$GDP_a <- ((GDP_3$gdp_ppp_mean.y/GDP_3$gdp_ppp_mean.x)^(1/length(2000:2021)))-1
```

```
# 3. change in income (base 2005) 【sensitivity analysis -- WTP (willingness to pay) --
```

```
http://oecdpublichealthexplorer.org/ncd-doc/Economy/VSL.html 】
```

```
GDP_base_2005 <- data.frame()  
for (i in list_204c_location_id) { # i=6  
  GDP_x <- GDP[GDP$location_id ==i, c("location_id","year","gdp_ppp_mean")]  
  GDP_x$n <- 0  
  for (y in c(2000:2004,2006:2021)) {  
    GDP_x$n[GDP_x$year==y] <- length(y:2005)  
  }  
  GDP_x$gdp_ppp_mean_base <- GDP_x$gdp_ppp_mean[GDP_x$year == 2005]  
  GDP_x$GDP_a_base2005 <-
```

```
((GDP_x$gdp_ppp_mean/GDP_x$gdp_ppp_mean_base)^(1/GDP_x$n))-1
  GDP_base_2005 <- rbind(GDP_base_2005,GDP_x[,c("location_id","year","GDP_a_base2005")])
}
```

4. y: the social discount rate

```
data_for_EB$y <- NA
data_for_EB$y[data_for_EB$location_id %in%
HIERARCHY$location_id[HIERARCHY$location_name_12 %in% c("World Bank High Income")]]
<- 0.03
data_for_EB$y[data_for_EB$location_id %in%
HIERARCHY$location_id[HIERARCHY$location_name_12 %in% c("World Bank Upper Middle
Income","")]] <- 0.04
data_for_EB$y[data_for_EB$location_id %in%
HIERARCHY$location_id[HIERARCHY$location_name_12 %in% c("World Bank Lower Middle
Income","World Bank Low Income")]] <- 0.05
```

5. GDP in each country in 2005 **【sensitivity analysis -- WTP】**

```
GDP_2005 <- GDP[GDP$location_id %in% list_204c_location_id & GDP$year
==2005,c("location_id","gdp_ppp_mean","gdp_ppp_lower","gdp_ppp_upper")]
names(GDP_2005) <- c("location_id","GDP_2005_m","GDP_2005_l","GDP_2005_u")
```

```
data_for_EB <- merge(data_for_EB,GDP_3[,c("location_id","GDP_a")],by= c("location_id"),all=T)
data_for_EB <-
merge(data_for_EB,GDP_base_2005[,c("location_id","year","GDP_a_base2005")],by=
c("location_id","year"),all=T)
data_for_EB <- merge(data_for_EB,GDP_2005,by= c("location_id"),all=T)
summary(data_for_EB$GDP_a)
summary(data_for_EB$GDP_a_base2005)
summary(is.na(data_for_EB$GDP_a))
summary(is.na(data_for_EB$GDP_a_base2005))
```

6. change in productive, represented by CPI **【sensitivity analysis -- WTP】**

```
# Source: Worldbank (https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/FP.CPI.TOTL.ZG?name\_desc=true)
# Note: Missing values are replaced with CPI values from low-income, lower-middle-income,
upper-middle-income, high-income regions, or global data.
CPI_raw <- read.csv("CPI.csv")
data_for_EB <-
merge(data_for_EB,CPI_raw[,c("year","location_id","CPI")],by=c("year","location_id"),all=T)
summary(data_for_EB$CPI)
summary(is.na(data_for_EB))
```

7. other parameters **【sensitivity analysis -- WTP】**

```
# The OECD base value of USD 3 million in year 2005 is the starting point for the calculation of VSL
values both for OECD countries and for other countries
```

```

VSL_OECD_2005 <- 3000000
# purchasing power parity (PPP)-adjusted USD estimates of the OECD in 2005
(https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.PP.KD)
GDP_OECD_2005 <- 43118.06
# income elasticity
B <- 0.8

```

```

# Part 4.4 Uncertainty analysis

```

```

calculate_ratio_sum <- function(a, y, t) {
  ratio_sum <- 0
  if(!is.na(t)){
    ratio_sum <- 0
    for (i in 1:t) {
      ratio <- ((1 + a)^i) / ((1 + y)^i)
      ratio_sum <- ratio_sum + ratio
    }
  }
  return(ratio_sum)
}

```

```

fun_avoid_economic_burden_main <- function(sap){
  #sap=4

```

```

  #N
  set.seed(sap)
  data_for_EB$avoid_DB_num_un <-
  rnorm(nrow(data_for_EB),data_for_EB$avoid_DB_num_un_m,

```

```

  (data_for_EB$avoid_DB_num_un_u-data_for_EB$avoid_DB_num_un_l)/(2*1.96))

```

```

  seed_counter <- sap+500
  while(any(data_for_EB["avoid_DB_num_un"] < 0)) {
    set.seed(seed_counter)
    negative_indices <- which(data_for_EB["avoid_DB_num_un"] < 0)
    data_for_EB[negative_indices,"avoid_DB_num_un"] <- rnorm(length(negative_indices),

```

```

  data_for_EB[negative_indices,"avoid_DB_num_un_m"],

```

```

  (data_for_EB[negative_indices,"avoid_DB_num_un_u"]-data_for_EB[negative_indices,"avoid_DB_n
um_un_l"])/(2*1.96))

```

```

  seed_counter <- seed_counter + 500
}

```

```

#GDP

```

```

set.seed(sap)
data_for_EB$GDP_un <- rnorm(nrow(data_for_EB),data_for_EB$gdp_ppp_mean,

(data_for_EB$gdp_ppp_upper-data_for_EB$gdp_ppp_lower)/(2*1.96))
seed_counter <- sap+500
while(any(data_for_EB["GDP_un"] < 0)) {
  set.seed(seed_counter)
  negative_indices <- which(data_for_EB["GDP_un"] < 0)
  data_for_EB[negative_indices,"GDP_un"] <- rnorm(length(negative_indices),

data_for_EB[negative_indices,"gdp_ppp_mean"],

(data_for_EB[negative_indices,"gdp_ppp_upper"]-data_for_EB[negative_indices,"gdp_ppp_lower"])/
(2*1.96))
  seed_counter <- seed_counter + 500
}

#avoidable economic burden
data_for_EB$ratio_sum <- mapply(calculate_ratio_sum, data_for_EB$GDP_a, data_for_EB$y,
data_for_EB$t)
data_for_EB$avoid_EB_num_un <- data_for_EB$avoid_DB_num_un_m * data_for_EB$GDP_un
* data_for_EB$ratio_sum

###WTP
#GDP_2005
set.seed(sap)
data_for_EB$GDP_2005_un <- rnorm(nrow(data_for_EB),data_for_EB$GDP_2005_m,

(data_for_EB$GDP_2005_u-data_for_EB$GDP_2005_l)/(2*1.96))
seed_counter <- sap+500
while(any(data_for_EB["GDP_2005_un"] < 0)) {
  set.seed(seed_counter)
  negative_indices <- which(data_for_EB["GDP_2005_un"] < 0)
  data_for_EB[negative_indices,"GDP_2005_un"] <- rnorm(length(negative_indices),

data_for_EB[negative_indices,"GDP_2005_m"],

(data_for_EB[negative_indices,"GDP_2005_u"]-data_for_EB[negative_indices,"GDP_2005_l"])/(2*1.
96))
  seed_counter <- seed_counter + 500
}

```

```

data_for_EB$avoid_EB_num_WTP_un <-
data_for_EB$avoid_DB_num_un*VSL_OECD_2005*((data_for_EB$GDP_2005_un/GDP_OECD_2
005)^B)*((1+data_for_EB$GDP_a_base2005+data_for_EB$CPI)^B)

```

```

data_for_EB$sap <- sap

```

```

if(min(data_for_EB$avoid_EB_num_un) <0 |
min(data_for_EB$avoid_EB_num_WTP_un)){print(paste0("Error: ",sap))}
print(sap)
return(data_for_EB)
}

```

```

result_list <- vector("list",n)
for (s in 1:n) {
  result_list[[s]] <- fun_avoid_economic_burden_main(s)
}
result_avoid_EB <- do.call(rbind, result_list)

```

```

# Aggregate the results:

```

```

# 1. country/territory level:

```

```

# (1) sum (by location_id, measure, analysis, simulations)

```

```

# (2) mean+95%UI (by location_id,analysis,measure)

```

```

result_avoid_EB_204c <- aggregate(cbind(avoid_EB_num_un, avoid_EB_num_WTP_un) ~
location_id + analysis + sap,

```

```

                                data = result_avoid_EB, FUN = sum)

```

```

result_avoid_EB_204c_1 <- result_avoid_EB_204c %>%

```

```

  group_by(location_id,analysis) %>%

```

```

  summarise(

```

```

    avoid_EB_num_un_m = mean(avoid_EB_num_un, na.rm = TRUE),

```

```

    avoid_EB_num_un_l = quantile(avoid_EB_num_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),

```

```

    avoid_EB_num_un_u = quantile(avoid_EB_num_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE),

```

```

    avoid_EB_num_WTP_un_m = mean(avoid_EB_num_WTP_un, na.rm = TRUE),

```

```

    avoid_EB_num_WTP_un_l = quantile(avoid_EB_num_WTP_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),

```

```

    avoid_EB_num_WTP_un_u = quantile(avoid_EB_num_WTP_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE)

```

```

  )

```

```

## Categorized the 204 countries (territories) into different groups

```

```

result_avoid_EB_204c_2 <- merge(HIERARCHY,result_avoid_EB_204c,by="location_id")

```

```

result_avoid_EB_204c_3 <-

```

```

merge(HIERARCHY[,c("location_id","location_name")],result_avoid_EB_204c_1,by="location_id")

```

```

# global

```

```

result_avoid_EB_all_1 <- aggregate(cbind(avoid_EB_num_un, avoid_EB_num_WTP_un) ~

```

```

location_id_11+location_name_11+ analysis + sap,
                                data = result_avoid_EB_204c_2, FUN = sum)
result_avoid_EB_all_1 <- result_avoid_EB_all_1 %>%
  group_by(location_id_11,location_name_11, analysis) %>%
  summarise(
    avoid_EB_num_un_m = mean(avoid_EB_num_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_EB_num_un_l = quantile(avoid_EB_num_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_EB_num_un_u = quantile(avoid_EB_num_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_EB_num_WTP_un_m = mean(avoid_EB_num_WTP_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_EB_num_WTP_un_l = quantile(avoid_EB_num_WTP_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_EB_num_WTP_un_u = quantile(avoid_EB_num_WTP_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE)
  )
names(result_avoid_EB_all_1)[names(result_avoid_EB_all_1) %in%
c("location_id_11","location_name_11")] <- c("location_id","location_name")
result_avoid_EB_all_1$location_level <- 1

write.csv(result_avoid_EB_all_1,paste0(loc_save,"result_avoid_EB_all_1_",unique(result_avoid_EB
$analysis),"_",n,".csv"),row.names = F)

result_avoid_EB_all_1 <-
as.data.frame(result_avoid_EB_all_1[names(result_avoid_EB_all_1)[!names(result_avoid_EB_all_1)
%in%
c("analysis","avoid_EB_num_WTP_un_m","avoid_EB_num_WTP_un_l","avoid_EB_num_WTP_un
_u")]])

# four World Bank income levels
result_avoid_EB_all_2 <- aggregate(cbind(avoid_EB_num_un) ~ location_id_12+location_name_12+
sap,
                                data = result_avoid_EB_204c_2, FUN = sum)
result_avoid_EB_all_2 <- result_avoid_EB_all_2 %>%
  group_by(location_id_12,location_name_12) %>%
  summarise(
    avoid_EB_num_un_m = mean(avoid_EB_num_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_EB_num_un_l = quantile(avoid_EB_num_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_EB_num_un_u = quantile(avoid_EB_num_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE)
  )
names(result_avoid_EB_all_2)[names(result_avoid_EB_all_2) %in%
c("location_id_12","location_name_12")] <- c("location_id","location_name")
result_avoid_EB_all_2$location_level <- 2
result_avoid_EB_all_2 <- result_avoid_EB_all_2[result_avoid_EB_all_2$location_id!=5,]

# twenty-one GBD regions
result_avoid_EB_all_3 <- aggregate(cbind(avoid_EB_num_un) ~ location_id_13+location_name_13+
sap,

```

```

data = result_avoid_EB_204c_2, FUN = sum)
result_avoid_EB_all_3 <- result_avoid_EB_all_3 %>%
  group_by(location_id_l3, location_name_l3) %>%
  summarise(
    avoid_EB_num_un_m = mean(avoid_EB_num_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_EB_num_un_l = quantile(avoid_EB_num_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_EB_num_un_u = quantile(avoid_EB_num_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE)
  )
names(result_avoid_EB_all_3)[names(result_avoid_EB_all_3) %in%
c("location_id_l3", "location_name_l3")] <- c("location_id", "location_name")
result_avoid_EB_all_3$location_level <- 3

result_avoid_EB_all_4 <- result_avoid_EB_204c_3[result_avoid_EB_204c_3$analysis=="main",
names(result_avoid_EB_204c_3)[names(result_avoid_EB_204c_3) %in%
names(result_avoid_EB_all_1)]]
result_avoid_EB_all_4$location_level <- 4

result_avoid_EB_all <- rbind(result_avoid_EB_all_1, result_avoid_EB_all_2, result_avoid_EB_all_3,
result_avoid_EB_all_4)
result_avoid_EB_all <-
result_avoid_EB_all[order(result_avoid_EB_all$location_level, result_avoid_EB_all$location_id),]

result_avoid_EB_all$avoid_EB_num_Billion <-
paste0(sprintf("%.2f", result_avoid_EB_all$avoid_EB_num_un_m/1000000000),
(",sprintf("%.2f", result_avoid_EB_all$avoid_EB_num_un_l/1000000000),",
",sprintf("%.2f", result_avoid_EB_all$avoid_EB_num_un_u/1000000000),")")
result_avoid_EB_all$avoid_EB_num_Million <-
paste0(sprintf("%.2f", result_avoid_EB_all$avoid_EB_num_un_m/1000000),
(",sprintf("%.2f", result_avoid_EB_all$avoid_EB_num_un_l/1000000),",
",sprintf("%.2f", result_avoid_EB_all$avoid_EB_num_un_u/1000000),")")
result_avoid_EB_all$avoid_EB_num <-
paste0(sprintf("%.2f", result_avoid_EB_all$avoid_EB_num_un_m),
(",sprintf("%.2f", result_avoid_EB_all$avoid_EB_num_un_l),",
",sprintf("%.2f", result_avoid_EB_all$avoid_EB_num_un_u),")")
result_avoid_EB_all_t <-
result_avoid_EB_all[,c("location_name", "avoid_EB_num", "avoid_EB_num_Million", "avoid_EB_num_Billion", "avoid_EB_num_un_m")]
names(result_avoid_EB_all_t) <- c("Location", "Preventable economic loss (US$)", "Preventable economic loss (million US$)", "Preventable economic loss (billion US$)", "preventable_EB_num_un_m")

write.csv(result_avoid_EB_all_t, paste0(loc_save, "/Table S_Preventable economic burden_main", "_", n, ".csv"), row.names = F)

```

```

#####
## Part 5 Sensitivity analysis of the avoidable burdens of NCDs
#####
for (a_c in c("sen1","sen2","sen3","sen4","sen5","sen6","sen7","sen8")) { # a_c="sen1"

# 1. Disease burden
result_list <- vector("list",n)
for (s in 1:n) {
  result_list[[s]] <- fun_avoid_disease_burden_main(sap=s,analysis_code=a_c)
}
result_avoid_DB <- do.call(rbind, result_list)

result_avoid_DB_204c <- aggregate(cbind(avoid_DB_num_un, base_burden_un) ~ location_id +
measure + analysis + sap,
                               data = result_avoid_DB, FUN = sum)
result_avoid_DB_204c_2 <- merge(HIERARCHY,result_avoid_DB_204c,by="location_id")

# global
result_avoid_DB_all_1 <- aggregate(cbind(avoid_DB_num_un, base_burden_un) ~
location_id_11+location_name_11+measure + analysis + sap,
                                  data = result_avoid_DB_204c_2, FUN = sum)
result_avoid_DB_all_1$avoid_DB_pro_un <-
result_avoid_DB_all_1$avoid_DB_num_un/result_avoid_DB_all_1$base_burden_un*100
result_avoid_DB_all_1 <- result_avoid_DB_all_1 %>%
  group_by(location_id_11,location_name_11, analysis, measure) %>%
  summarise(
    avoid_DB_num_un_m = mean(avoid_DB_num_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_num_un_l = quantile(avoid_DB_num_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_num_un_u = quantile(avoid_DB_num_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_pro_un_m = mean(avoid_DB_pro_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_pro_un_l = quantile(avoid_DB_pro_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_pro_un_u = quantile(avoid_DB_pro_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE)
  )
names(result_avoid_DB_all_1)[names(result_avoid_DB_all_1) %in%
c("location_id_11","location_name_11")] <- c("location_id","location_name")
result_avoid_DB_all_1$location_level <- 1

write.csv(result_avoid_DB_all_1,paste0(loc_save,"/result_avoid_DB_all_1_",unique(result_avoid_D
B$analysis),"_",n,".csv"),row.names = F)

```

```

# 2. Economic burden
# t: the average number of life-years lost
# age- and sex-specific avoidable NCDs-related deaths
data_N <- result_avoid_DB[result_avoid_DB$measure == "Deaths",]
data_N_1 <- data_N %>%
  group_by(analysis,location_id,year,age_id,sex_id) %>%
  summarise(
    avoid_DB_num_un_m = mean(avoid_DB_num_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_num_un_l = quantile(avoid_DB_num_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_num_un_u = quantile(avoid_DB_num_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE)
  )

t_data <- merge(data_N_1,Life_table,by=c("location_id","year","age_id","sex_id"))
t_data$avoid_DB_num_un_m_xLE <- t_data$avoid_DB_num_un_m*t_data$
t_data_1 <- t_data %>%
  group_by(analysis,location_id, year) %>%
  dplyr::summarize(
    NxLE_m = sum(avoid_DB_num_un_m_xLE),
    N_m = sum(avoid_DB_num_un_m)
  )
t_data_1$t <- as.integer(ceiling(t_data_1$NxLE_m/t_data_1$N_m))
summary(t_data_1$t)
summary(t_data_1$N_m[is.na(t_data_1$t)])

# N: number of avoidable NCDs-related deaths
data_N_2 <- data_N %>%
  group_by(analysis,location_id,year) %>%
  summarise(
    avoid_DB_num_un_m = mean(avoid_DB_num_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_num_un_l = quantile(avoid_DB_num_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_DB_num_un_u = quantile(avoid_DB_num_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE)
  )

data_for_EB <- merge(data_N_2,t_data_1[,c("analysis","location_id","year","t")], by=
c("analysis","location_id","year"),all=T)
data_for_EB <- merge(data_for_EB,GDP,by= c("location_id","year"),all=T)
data_for_EB <- merge(data_for_EB,GDP_3[,c("location_id","GDP_a")],by=
c("location_id"),all=T)
data_for_EB <-
merge(data_for_EB,GDP_base_2005[,c("location_id","year","GDP_a_base2005")],by=
c("location_id","year"),all=T)

```

```

data_for_EB <- merge(data_for_EB,GDP_2005,by= c("location_id"),all=T)
data_for_EB$y <- NA
data_for_EB$y[data_for_EB$location_id %in%
HIERARCHY$location_id[HIERARCHY$location_name_l2 %in% c("World Bank High Income")]]
<- 0.03
data_for_EB$y[data_for_EB$location_id %in%
HIERARCHY$location_id[HIERARCHY$location_name_l2 %in% c("World Bank Upper Middle
Income","/")]] <- 0.04
data_for_EB$y[data_for_EB$location_id %in%
HIERARCHY$location_id[HIERARCHY$location_name_l2 %in% c("World Bank Lower Middle
Income","World Bank Low Income")]] <- 0.05
data_for_EB <-
merge(data_for_EB,CPI_raw[,c("year","location_id","CPI")],by=c("year","location_id"),all=T)

result_list <- vector("list",n)
for (s in 1:n) {
  result_list[[s]] <- fun_avoid_economic_burden_main(s)
}
result_avoid_EB <- do.call(rbind, result_list)

result_avoid_EB_204c <- aggregate(cbind(avoid_EB_num_un, avoid_EB_num_WTP_un) ~
location_id + analysis + sap,
                                data = result_avoid_EB, FUN = sum)
result_avoid_EB_204c_2 <- merge(HIERARCHY,result_avoid_EB_204c,by="location_id")

# global
result_avoid_EB_all_1 <- aggregate(cbind(avoid_EB_num_un, avoid_EB_num_WTP_un) ~
location_id_l1+location_name_l1+ analysis + sap,
                                data = result_avoid_EB_204c_2, FUN = sum)
result_avoid_EB_all_1 <- result_avoid_EB_all_1 %>%
  group_by(location_id_l1,location_name_l1, analysis) %>%
  summarise(
    avoid_EB_num_un_m = mean(avoid_EB_num_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_EB_num_un_l = quantile(avoid_EB_num_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_EB_num_un_u = quantile(avoid_EB_num_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_EB_num_WTP_un_m = mean(avoid_EB_num_WTP_un, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_EB_num_WTP_un_l = quantile(avoid_EB_num_WTP_un, 0.025, na.rm = TRUE),
    avoid_EB_num_WTP_un_u = quantile(avoid_EB_num_WTP_un, 0.975, na.rm = TRUE)
  )
names(result_avoid_EB_all_1)[names(result_avoid_EB_all_1) %in%
c("location_id_l1","location_name_l1")] <- c("location_id","location_name")
result_avoid_EB_all_1$location_level <- 1

```

```
write.csv(result_avoid_EB_all_1,paste0(loc_save,"/result_avoid_EB_all_1_",unique(result_avoid_EB
$analysis),"_",n,".csv"),row.names = F)
```

```
  print(a_c)
}
```

```
# Analysis sensitivity
```

```
for (i in c("main","sen1","sen2","sen3","sen4","sen5","sen6","sen7","sen8")) {
```

```
  assign(paste0("result_avoid_DB_all_1_",i),read.csv(paste0(loc_save,"/result_avoid_DB_all_1_",i,"_",
n,".csv")))

```

```
  assign(paste0("result_avoid_EB_all_1_",i),read.csv(paste0(loc_save,"/result_avoid_EB_all_1_",i,"_",
n,".csv")))
}
```

```
result_avoid_DB_all_1 <- rbind(result_avoid_DB_all_1_main,result_avoid_DB_all_1_sen1,
                               result_avoid_DB_all_1_sen2,result_avoid_DB_all_1_sen3,
                               result_avoid_DB_all_1_sen4,result_avoid_DB_all_1_sen5,
                               result_avoid_DB_all_1_sen6,result_avoid_DB_all_1_sen7,
                               result_avoid_DB_all_1_sen8)
```

```
result_avoid_EB_all_1 <- rbind(result_avoid_EB_all_1_main,result_avoid_EB_all_1_sen1,
                               result_avoid_EB_all_1_sen2,result_avoid_EB_all_1_sen3,
                               result_avoid_EB_all_1_sen4,result_avoid_EB_all_1_sen5,
                               result_avoid_EB_all_1_sen6,result_avoid_EB_all_1_sen7,
                               result_avoid_EB_all_1_sen8)
```

```
result_avoid_DB_all_1$avoid_DB_num <-
paste0(sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_DB_all_1$avoid_DB_num_un_m/1000000),"
(",sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_DB_all_1$avoid_DB_num_un_l/1000000),"
",sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_DB_all_1$avoid_DB_num_un_u/1000000),")")
result_avoid_DB_all_1$avoid_DB_pro <-
paste0(sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_DB_all_1$avoid_DB_pro_un_m),"
(",sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_DB_all_1$avoid_DB_pro_un_l),"
",sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_DB_all_1$avoid_DB_pro_un_u),")")
result_avoid_DB_all_1_Deaths <- result_avoid_DB_all_1[result_avoid_DB_all_1$measure
=="Deaths",c("analysis","avoid_DB_num","avoid_DB_pro")]
names(result_avoid_DB_all_1_Deaths) <- c("analysis","avoid_Deaths_num","avoid_Deaths_pro")
result_avoid_DB_all_1_DALYs <- result_avoid_DB_all_1[result_avoid_DB_all_1$measure
```

```

=="DALYs",c("analysis","avoid_DB_num","avoid_DB_pro")]
names(result_avoid_DB_all_1_DALYs) <- c("analysis","avoid_DALYs_num","avoid_DALYs_pro")

result_avoid_DB_all_1 <- merge(result_avoid_DB_all_1_Deaths,result_avoid_DB_all_1_DALYs)
result_avoid_DB_all_1 <- rbind(result_avoid_DB_all_1,result_avoid_DB_all_1[1,])
result_avoid_DB_all_1[10,"analysis"] <- "sen9"

result_avoid_EB_all_1$avoid_EB_num_un <-
paste0(sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_EB_all_1$avoid_EB_num_un_m/1000000000),"
(",sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_EB_all_1$avoid_EB_num_un_l/1000000000),"
",sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_EB_all_1$avoid_EB_num_un_u/1000000000),")")
result_avoid_EB_all_1$avoid_EB_num_WTP_un <-
paste0(sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_EB_all_1$avoid_EB_num_WTP_un_m/1000000000),"
(",sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_EB_all_1$avoid_EB_num_WTP_un_l/1000000000),"
",sprintf("%.2f",result_avoid_EB_all_1$avoid_EB_num_WTP_un_u/1000000000),")")

result_avoid_EB_all_1_1 <- result_avoid_EB_all_1[,c("analysis","avoid_EB_num_un")]
result_avoid_EB_all_1_2 <-
result_avoid_EB_all_1[result_avoid_EB_all_1$analysis=="main",c("analysis","avoid_EB_num_WTP
_un")]
result_avoid_EB_all_1_2$analysis <- "sen9"
names(result_avoid_EB_all_1_2) <- c("analysis","avoid_EB_num_un")
result_avoid_EB_all_1 <- rbind(result_avoid_EB_all_1_1,result_avoid_EB_all_1_2)

result_sensi <- merge(result_avoid_DB_all_1,result_avoid_EB_all_1)
result_sensi$analysis <- sub("sen","S",result_sensi$analysis)
names(result_sensi) <- c("analysis","preventable_Deaths_num","preventable_Deaths_pro",

"preventable_DALYs_num","preventable_DALYs_pro","preventable_EB_num_un")

write.csv(result_sensi,paste0(loc_save,"/Table S_Preventable burden_Sensitivity
analysis.csv"),row.names=F)

```

```

# Visualization
library(ggplot2)
library(treemapify)
library(RColorBrewer)
library(sf)
library(dplyr)
library(grid)

```

```

result_avoid_DB_all_t <- read.csv(paste0(loc_save, "/Table S_Preventable disease
burden_main", "_", "n", ".csv"))
result_avoid_EB_all_t <- read.csv(paste0(loc_save, "/Table S_preventable economic
burden_main", "_", "n", ".csv"))

result_avoid_DB_all_t_p1 <- result_avoid_DB_all_t[3:52,]
result_avoid_DB_all_t_p1$Cat <- "21 GBD regions"
result_avoid_DB_all_t_p1[1:8,"Cat"] <- "4 World Bank income levels"
result_avoid_DB_all_t_p1$preventable_DB_num_un_m_millin <-
result_avoid_DB_all_t_p1$preventable_DB_num_un_m/1000000

result_avoid_EB_all_t_p1 <- result_avoid_EB_all_t[2:26,]
result_avoid_EB_all_t_p1$Cat <- "21 GBD regions"
result_avoid_EB_all_t_p1[1:4,"Cat"] <- "4 World Bank income levels"
result_avoid_EB_all_t_p1$preventable_EB_num_un_m_billion <-
result_avoid_EB_all_t_p1$preventable_EB_num_un_m/1000000000

theme_0 <- theme(legend.text = element_text(size = 10, family = "serif",color = "black"),
                legend.title=element_text(size=10, family = "serif",color = "black"),
                plot.title = element_text(vjust = 8,size=14, family = "serif",color = "black")
)

df <- result_avoid_DB_all_t_p1[result_avoid_DB_all_t_p1$Index == "Deaths",]
p <- ggplot(df, aes(area = preventable_DB_num_un_m_millin, fill =
preventable_DB_num_un_m_millin,
                label = Location, subgroup = Cat)) +
  geom_treemap() +
  geom_treemap_subgroup_border() +
  geom_treemap_subgroup_text(size=15, place = "bottomleft", alpha = 1, #grow = T,
                            colour = "white", fontface = "bold", min.size = 0, family = "serif")
+
  geom_treemap_text(size=12, colour = "black", place = "topleft", reflow = T, alpha=1, family =
"serif")+
  scale_fill_distiller(palette=c("Greens"), direction = 1)
p1 <- p+labs(fill = "Preventable deaths (M)", title = "A")+theme_0

df <- result_avoid_DB_all_t_p1[result_avoid_DB_all_t_p1$Index == "DALYs",]
p <- ggplot(df, aes(area = preventable_DB_num_un_m_millin, fill =
preventable_DB_num_un_m_millin,
                label = Location, subgroup = Cat)) +
  geom_treemap() +
  geom_treemap_subgroup_border() +

```

```

geom_treemap_subgroup_text(size=15,place = "bottomleft", alpha = 1, #grow = T,
                           colour ="white", fontface = "bold", min.size = 0, family = "serif")
+
geom_treemap_text(size=12,colour = "black", place = "topleft", reflow = T,alpha=1, family =
"serif")+
scale_fill_distiller(palette=c("Greens"),direction = 1)
p2 <- p+labs(fill = "Preventable DALYs (M) ",title = "B")+theme_0

```

```

df <- result_avoid_EB_all_t_p1
p <- ggplot(df, aes(area = preventable_EB_num_un_m_billion, fill =
preventable_EB_num_un_m_billion,
                 label = Location,subgroup = Cat)) +
  geom_treemap() +
  geom_treemap_subgroup_border() +
  geom_treemap_subgroup_text(size=15,place = "bottomleft", alpha = 1, #grow = T,
                             colour ="white", fontface = "bold", min.size = 0, family = "serif")
+
  geom_treemap_text(size=12,colour = "black", place = "topleft", reflow = T,alpha=1, family =
"serif")+
  scale_fill_distiller(palette=c("Greens"),direction = 1)
p3 <- p+labs(fill = "Preventable costs (B) ",title = "C")+theme_0

```

```

result_avoid_DB_all_t_p2 <- result_avoid_DB_all_t[53:nrow(result_avoid_DB_all_t),]
result_avoid_EB_all_t_p2 <- result_avoid_EB_all_t[27:nrow(result_avoid_EB_all_t),]
fiveL<-function(x){
  q0<-quantile(x,0,na.rm = T)
  q20<-quantile(x,0.20,na.rm = T)
  q40<-quantile(x,0.40,na.rm = T)
  q60<-quantile(x,0.60,na.rm = T)
  q80<-quantile(x,0.80,na.rm = T)
  dx<-rep(NA,length(x))
  dx[which(x<=q20)]<- paste0("Q1: < ",sprintf("%.1f",q20))
  dx[which(x>q20 & x<=q40)]<- paste0("Q2: ",sprintf("%.1f",q20), " - ",sprintf("%.1f",q40))
  dx[which(x>q40 & x<=q60)]<- paste0("Q3: ",sprintf("%.1f",q40), " - ",sprintf("%.1f",q60))
  dx[which(x>q60 & x<=q80)]<- paste0("Q4: ",sprintf("%.1f",q60), " - ",sprintf("%.1f",q80))
  dx[which(x>q80)]<-paste0("Q5: ≥ ",sprintf("%.1f",q80))
  return(dx)
}
mytheme_1 <- theme_bw()+
  theme(panel.grid.major = element_line(colour = NA),
        panel.grid.minor = element_blank(),
        axis.text = element_blank(),

```

```

axis.ticks = element_blank(),
axis.title = element_blank(),
text = element_text(size = 9, family = "serif",
                    color = "black"),
legend.text = element_text(size = 10, family = "serif",
                            color = "black"),
legend.title=element_text(size=10),
plot.margin = margin(t = 0,r = 0,b = 0,l = 0,unit = "cm"),
plot.title = element_text(size=14, family = "serif",color = "black"))
color_R = brewer.pal(n= 5, name = "Greens")

df <- result_avoid_DB_all_t_p2[result_avoid_DB_all_t_p2$Index=="Deaths",]
names(df)[names(df)=="Location"] <- "location_name"
df <- merge(df,HIERARCHY[,c("location_id","location_name")])
df$val <- fiveL(df$preventable_DB_num_un_m)
df <- dplyr::full_join(df, Map,by = c("location_id"))
df$val[is.na(df$val)] <- "No data"
table(df$val)
cols <- c("Q5: ≥ 6043.1" = color_R[5],
         "Q4: 2374.6 - 6043.1" = color_R[4],
         "Q3: 890.0 - 2374.6" = color_R[3],
         "Q2: 111.4 - 890.0" = color_R[2],
         "Q1: < 111.4" = color_R[1],
         "No data" = "grey90")
df$val <- factor(df$val,ordered = T,
               levels = c("Q5: ≥ 6043.1",
                         "Q4: 2374.6 - 6043.1",
                         "Q3: 890.0 - 2374.6",
                         "Q2: 111.4 - 890.0",
                         "Q1: < 111.4",
                         "No data"))

p4 <- ggplot(data = df)+
  geom_sf(aes(fill = val, geometry = `geometry`, color = val),alpha = 0.75, size = 0.1)+
  scale_color_manual(values = cols, aesthetics = c("colour", "fill"),
                    na.value = "grey90")+
  scale_x_continuous(expand = c(0,0))+
  scale_y_continuous(expand = c(0,0))+
  guides(color='none')+
  mytheme_1+theme(aspect.ratio=6/12,
                 panel.border = element_blank(),
                 legend.key.height = unit(11, "pt"),
                 legend.key.width = unit(12, "pt"),
                 legend.background=element_rect(fill=rgb(1,1,1,alpha=0.001),colour=NA),
                 plot.margin = margin(t = 0,r = 0,b = 0,l = 0,unit = "cm"))+

```

```

labs(fill = "Preventable deaths", title = "D")

df <- result_avoid_DB_all_t_p2[result_avoid_DB_all_t_p2$Index=="DALYs",]
names(df)[names(df)=="Location"] <- "location_name"
df <- merge(df,HIERARCHY[,c("location_id","location_name")])
df$val <- fiveL(df$preventable_DB_num_un_m)
df <- dplyr::full_join(df, Map,by = c("location_id"))
df$val[is.na(df$val)] <- "No data"
table(df$val)
cols <- c("Q5: ≥ 143847.4" = color_R[5],
          "Q4: 54932.0 - 143847.4" = color_R[4],
          "Q3: 20591.5 - 54932.0" = color_R[3],
          "Q2: 3009.3 - 20591.5" = color_R[2],
          "Q1: < 3009.3" = color_R[1],
          "No data" = "grey90")
df$val <- factor(df$val,ordered = T,
                levels = c("Q5: ≥ 143847.4",
                           "Q4: 54932.0 - 143847.4",
                           "Q3: 20591.5 - 54932.0",
                           "Q2: 3009.3 - 20591.5",
                           "Q1: < 3009.3",
                           "No data"))

p5 <- ggplot(data = df)+
  geom_sf(aes(fill = val, geometry = `geometry`, color = val),alpha = 0.75, size = 0.1)+
  scale_color_manual(values = cols, aesthetics = c("colour", "fill"),
                    na.value = "grey90")+
  scale_x_continuous(expand = c(0,0))+
  scale_y_continuous(expand = c(0,0))+
  guides(color='none')+
  mytheme_1+theme(aspect.ratio=6/12,
                  panel.border = element_blank(),
                  legend.key.height = unit(11, "pt"),
                  legend.key.width = unit(12, "pt"),
                  legend.background=element_rect(fill=rgb(1,1,1,alpha=0.001),colour=NA),
                  plot.margin = margin(t = 0,r = 0,b = 0,l = 0,unit = "cm"))+
  labs(fill = "Preventable DALYs", title = "E")

df <- result_avoid_EB_all_t_p2
names(df)[names(df)=="Location"] <- "location_name"
df <- merge(df,HIERARCHY[,c("location_id","location_name")])
df$val <- fiveL(df$preventable_EB_num_un_m/1000000)
df <- dplyr::full_join(df, Map,by = c("location_id"))
df$val[is.na(df$val)] <- "No data"
table(df$val)

```

```

cols <- c("Q5: ≥ 39.3" = color_R[5],
          "Q4: 8.0 - 39.3" = color_R[4],
          "Q3: 1.9 - 8.0" = color_R[3],
          "Q2: 0.3 - 1.9" = color_R[2],
          "Q1: < 0.3" = color_R[1],
          "No data" = "grey90")
df$val <- factor(df$val, ordered = T,
                levels = c("Q5: ≥ 39.3",
                           "Q4: 8.0 - 39.3",
                           "Q3: 1.9 - 8.0",
                           "Q2: 0.3 - 1.9",
                           "Q1: < 0.3",
                           "No data"))

p6 <- ggplot(data = df)+
  geom_sf(aes(fill = val, geometry = `geometry`, color = val), alpha = 0.75, size = 0.1)+
  scale_color_manual(values = cols, aesthetics = c("colour", "fill"),
                    na.value = "grey90")+
  scale_x_continuous(expand = c(0,0))+
  scale_y_continuous(expand = c(0,0))+
  guides(color='none')+
  mytheme_1+theme(aspect.ratio=6/12,
                  panel.border = element_blank(),
                  legend.key.height = unit(11, "pt"),
                  legend.key.width = unit(12, "pt"),
                  legend.background=element_rect(fill=rgb(1,1,1,alpha=0.001),colour=NA),
                  plot.margin = margin(t = 0,r = 0,b = 0,l = 0,unit = "cm"))+
  labs(fill = "Preventable costs (M)", title = "F")

grid.newpage()
pushViewport(viewport(layout = grid.layout(nrow=17,ncol = 9,
                                           widths = 3, heights =3)))
vplayout <- function(x,y){ viewport(layout.pos.row = x, layout.pos.col = y)}

print(p1, vp = vplayout(2:4,1:4))
print(p4, vp = vplayout(1:5,5:9))
print(p2, vp = vplayout(7:9,1:4))
print(p5, vp = vplayout(6:10,5:9))
print(p3, vp = vplayout(12:14,1:4))
print(p6, vp = vplayout(11:15,5:9))
# Manual export: 12*12 inches

```

```

#DB
#global
result_avoid_DB_all_t$Number.of.preventable.deaths..million.[result_avoid_DB_all_t$Location
=="Global" & result_avoid_DB_all_t$Index=="Deaths"]
result_avoid_DB_all_t$Number.of.preventable.deaths..million.[result_avoid_DB_all_t$Location
=="Global" & result_avoid_DB_all_t$Index=="DALYs"]
result_avoid_DB_all_t$Percentage.of.preventable.deaths....[result_avoid_DB_all_t$Location
=="Global" & result_avoid_DB_all_t$Index=="Deaths"]
result_avoid_DB_all_t$Percentage.of.preventable.deaths....[result_avoid_DB_all_t$Location
=="Global" & result_avoid_DB_all_t$Index=="DALYs"]
#WB
result_WB <- result_avoid_DB_all_t[3:10,]
#highest num
result_WB_1 <- result_WB[result_WB$Index=="Deaths",]
result_WB_1$Location[result_WB_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m ==
max(result_WB_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m)]
result_WB_1$Number.of.preventable.deaths..million.[result_WB_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m ==
max(result_WB_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m)]
result_WB_1 <- result_WB[result_WB$Index=="DALYs",]
result_WB_1$Location[result_WB_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m ==
max(result_WB_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m)]
result_WB_1$Number.of.preventable.deaths..million.[result_WB_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m ==
max(result_WB_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m)]
#lowest num
result_WB_1 <- result_WB[result_WB$Index=="Deaths",]
result_WB_1$Location[result_WB_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m ==
min(result_WB_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m)]
result_WB_1$Number.of.preventable.deaths..million.[result_WB_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m ==
min(result_WB_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m)]
result_WB_1 <- result_WB[result_WB$Index=="DALYs",]
result_WB_1$Location[result_WB_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m ==
min(result_WB_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m)]
result_WB_1$Number.of.preventable.deaths..million.[result_WB_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m ==
min(result_WB_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m)]
#highest pro
result_WB_1 <- result_WB[result_WB$Index=="Deaths",]
result_WB_1$Location[result_WB_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m ==
max(result_WB_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m)]
result_WB_1$Percentage.of.preventable.deaths....[result_WB_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m ==
max(result_WB_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m)]
result_WB_1 <- result_WB[result_WB$Index=="DALYs",]

```

```

result_WB_1$Location[result_WB_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m ==
max(result_WB_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m)]
result_WB_1$Percentage.of.preventable.deaths....[result_WB_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m ==
max(result_WB_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m)]
#lowest pro
result_WB_1 <- result_WB[result_WB$Index=="Deaths",]
result_WB_1$Location[result_WB_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m ==
min(result_WB_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m)]
result_WB_1$Percentage.of.preventable.deaths....[result_WB_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m ==
min(result_WB_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m)]
result_WB_1 <- result_WB[result_WB$Index=="DALYs",]
result_WB_1$Location[result_WB_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m ==
min(result_WB_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m)]
result_WB_1$Percentage.of.preventable.deaths....[result_WB_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m ==
min(result_WB_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m)]

#21region
result_21R <- result_avoid_DB_all_t[11:52,]
#highest num
result_21R_1 <- result_21R[result_21R$Index=="Deaths",]
result_21R_1$Location[result_21R_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m ==
max(result_21R_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m)]
result_21R_1$Number.of.preventable.deaths..million.[result_21R_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m ==
max(result_21R_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m)]
result_21R_1 <- result_21R[result_21R$Index=="DALYs",]
result_21R_1$Location[result_21R_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m ==
max(result_21R_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m)]
result_21R_1$Number.of.preventable.deaths..million.[result_21R_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m ==
max(result_21R_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m)]
#lowest num
result_21R_1 <- result_21R[result_21R$Index=="Deaths",]
result_21R_1$Location[result_21R_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m ==
min(result_21R_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m)]
result_21R_1$Number.of.preventable.deaths..million.[result_21R_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m ==
min(result_21R_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m)]
result_21R_1 <- result_21R[result_21R$Index=="DALYs",]
result_21R_1$Location[result_21R_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m ==
min(result_21R_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m)]
result_21R_1$Number.of.preventable.deaths..million.[result_21R_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m ==
min(result_21R_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m)]
#highest pro
result_21R_1 <- result_21R[result_21R$Index=="Deaths",]
result_21R_1$Location[result_21R_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m ==
max(result_21R_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m)]

```

```

result_21R_1$Percentage.of.preventable.deaths....[result_21R_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m ==
max(result_21R_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m)]
result_21R_1 <- result_21R[result_21R$Index=="DALYs",]
result_21R_1$Location[result_21R_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m ==
max(result_21R_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m)]
result_21R_1$Percentage.of.preventable.deaths....[result_21R_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m ==
max(result_21R_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m)]
#lowest pro
result_21R_1 <- result_21R[result_21R$Index=="Deaths",]
result_21R_1$Location[result_21R_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m ==
min(result_21R_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m)]
result_21R_1$Percentage.of.preventable.deaths....[result_21R_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m ==
min(result_21R_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m)]
result_21R_1 <- result_21R[result_21R$Index=="DALYs",]
result_21R_1$Location[result_21R_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m ==
min(result_21R_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m)]
result_21R_1$Percentage.of.preventable.deaths....[result_21R_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m ==
min(result_21R_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m)]

```

#204 country

```
result_204c <- result_avoid_DB_all_t[53:nrow(result_avoid_DB_all_t),]
```

#highest num

```
result_204c_1 <- result_204c[result_204c$Index=="Deaths",]
```

```
result_204c_1$Location[result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m %in%
```

```
result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m,
decreasing = TRUE)[1:3]]]
```

```
result_204c_1$Number.of.preventable.deaths..million.[result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m %
in% result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m,
decreasing = TRUE)[1:3]]]
```

```
result_204c_1 <- result_204c[result_204c$Index=="DALYs",]
```

```
result_204c_1$Location[result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m %in%
```

```
result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m,
decreasing = TRUE)[1:3]]]
```

```
result_204c_1$Number.of.preventable.deaths..million.[result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m %
in% result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m,
decreasing = TRUE)[1:3]]]
```

#lowest num

```
result_204c_1 <- result_204c[result_204c$Index=="Deaths",]
```

```
result_204c_1$Location[result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m %in%
```

```
result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m,
decreasing = F)[1:3]]]
```

```
result_204c_1$Number.of.preventable.deaths..million.[result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m %
in% result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m,
decreasing = TRUE)[1:3]]]
```

```

result_204c_1 <- result_204c[result_204c$Index=="DALYs",]
result_204c_1$Location[result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m %in%
result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m,
decreasing = F)[1:3]]]
result_204c_1$Number.of.preventable.deaths..million.[result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m %
in% result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_DB_num_un_m,
decreasing = TRUE)[1:3]]]
#highest pro
result_204c_1 <- result_204c[result_204c$Index=="Deaths",]
result_204c_1$Location[result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m %in%
result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m,
decreasing = TRUE)[1:3]]]
result_204c_1$Percentage.of.preventable.deaths...[result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m %in%
result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m,
decreasing = TRUE)[1:3]]]
result_204c_1 <- result_204c[result_204c$Index=="DALYs",]
result_204c_1$Location[result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m %in%
result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m,
decreasing = TRUE)[1:3]]]
result_204c_1$Percentage.of.preventable.deaths...[result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m %in%
result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m,
decreasing = TRUE)[1:3]]]
#lowest pro
result_204c_1 <- result_204c[result_204c$Index=="Deaths",]
result_204c_1$Location[result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m %in%
result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m,
decreasing = F)[1:3]]]
result_204c_1$Percentage.of.preventable.deaths...[result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m %in%
result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m,
decreasing = TRUE)[1:3]]]
result_204c_1 <- result_204c[result_204c$Index=="DALYs",]
result_204c_1$Location[result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m %in%
result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m,
decreasing = F)[1:3]]]
result_204c_1$Percentage.of.preventable.deaths...[result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m %in%
result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_DB_pro_un_m,
decreasing = TRUE)[1:3]]]

#EB
#global
result_avoid_EB_all_t$Preventable.economic.loss..billion.US..[result_avoid_EB_all_t$Location=="Gl
obal"]

```

```

#WB
result_WB_1 <- result_avoid_EB_all_t[2:5,]
#highest num
result_WB_1$Location[result_WB_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m==max(result_WB_1$preventable_
EB_num_un_m)]
result_WB_1$Preventable.economic.loss..billion.US..[result_WB_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m==m
ax(result_WB_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m)]
#lowest num
result_WB_1$Location[result_WB_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m==min(result_WB_1$preventable_
EB_num_un_m)]
result_WB_1$Preventable.economic.loss..billion.US..[result_WB_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m==m
in(result_WB_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m)]

#21 region
result_21R_1 <- result_avoid_EB_all_t[6:26,]
#highest num
result_21R_1$Location[result_21R_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m==max(result_21R_1$preventable
_EB_num_un_m)]
result_21R_1$Preventable.economic.loss..billion.US..[result_21R_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m==
max(result_21R_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m)]
#lowest num
result_21R_1$Location[result_21R_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m==min(result_21R_1$preventable_
EB_num_un_m)]
result_21R_1$Preventable.economic.loss..million.US..[result_21R_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m==
min(result_21R_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m)]

#204 countries
result_204c_1 <- result_avoid_EB_all_t[27:nrow(result_avoid_EB_all_t),]
#highest num
result_204c_1$Location[result_204c_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m%in%
result_204c_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m,
decreasing = T)[1:3]]]
result_204c_1$Preventable.economic.loss..billion.US..[result_204c_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m%i
n% result_204c_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m,
decreasing = T)[1:3]]]
#lowest num
result_204c_1$Location[result_204c_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m%in%
result_204c_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m,
decreasing = F)[1:3]]]
result_204c_1$Preventable.economic.loss..US..[result_204c_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m%in%
result_204c_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m[order(result_204c_1$preventable_EB_num_un_m,
decreasing = F)[1:3]]]

```